

Artificial Cells that Reproduce Using Spatially Distributed Asynchronous Parallel Processes

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Abstract

Replication time is among the most important components of a bacterial cell's reproductive fitness. Paradoxically, larger cells replicate in less time than smaller cells despite the fact that assembling a larger cell requires collecting and combining increased quantities of raw materials. This feat is accomplished through the prodigious use of parallel processing, chiefly the translation of mRNA into protein by tens of thousands of ribosomes acting in parallel. The massive over-expression of ribosomes permits protein synthesis, the limiting step in replication, to occur at a rate and scale that would be otherwise impossible. In computer science, spatial parallelism is the distribution of work across the nodes of a distributed-memory multicomputer system. Despite the fact that a non-negligible fraction of artificial life research is grounded in spatially parallel substrates, there have been no examples of artificial organisms that exploit spatial parallelism to replicate in less time than smaller organisms. This paper describes artificial cells defined in a combinator-based artificial chemistry that replicate in less time than smaller cells. This is achieved by employing extra copies of programs implementing the limiting steps in the process used by the cells to synthesize their component parts.

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1 Introduction

On Earth, the origin of life and its evolution into organisms of increasing complexity was facilitated by our universe’s rich physics, the early Earth’s bountiful solar, geothermal and chemical energy resources, the massive volume of its prehistoric marine environment, and the vast scale of geologic time. The field of artificial life is premised on the idea that artificial systems can be constructed which, through simplifications and other economies of design, are capable of analogous displays of emergence and open-ended evolution, but on vastly shorter time scales within the memories of digital computers.

Any attempt to demonstrate the evolution of organisms of increasing complexity in an artificial system should begin with an attempt to define complexity itself. Unfortunately, measures based on difficulty of description such as Kolmogorov complexity [Kolmogorov, 1965] suffer from the drawback that random objects have longer descriptions than non-random objects. Measures based on difficulty of creation, such as Bennett’s *logical depth* [Bennett, 1988], improve on this by defining complexity as the time required to generate an object from its shortest description. This is an interesting move, and does seem to solve the problem, but it introduces a new one: since duplication increases generative cost, it rewards duplication for its own sake. Combining the best of both ideas, Gell-Mann and Lloyd [2003] proposed that complexity be restricted to non-random and non-duplicated structure.

Unfortunately, the restriction to non-random structure lacks explanatory force. What is needed is not just a criterion for what information counts and what information does not, but an explanation of why one should and one should not. Deutsch hypothesized that the relevant distinction is between information adapted to a context and information that is not [Deutsch, 1997]. This is explanatory because information adapted to a context acquires meaning through its utility in that context. Pattee’s closely related framework makes this biologically concrete: in a self-reproducing system, the crucial complexity does not reside in the *non-contingent* organization of the environment, but in the symbolically mediated *contingent* organization internal to the system itself [Pattee, 1995].

This discussion has focused on both difficulty of description and difficulty of creation. Strikingly, living organisms contain descriptions of themselves and use these to create copies of themselves — difficulty of description and difficulty of construction are thus inextricably related. For a self-description to be copied and translated into a new organism, it must be physically instantiated as a material object. This means that increases in complexity of living things have a physical cost: complex organisms require more material resources to reproduce than simpler organisms. These costs are the most fundamental selection pressures acting on the information embodied in self-descriptions. In biological systems, the relevant contexts are environmental niches, and natural selection is the process by which self-descriptions become adapted to them. This connects closely to Adami’s view of biological complexity as information about the environment acquired under selection [Adami et al., 2000], and to Pattee’s emphasis on how causal organization transfers from the stable structure of the environment into the contingent, self-interpreting organization of living systems [Pattee, 1995].

Replication time is among the most important components of a bacterial cell’s reproductive fitness. The faster a bacterium replicates, the more likely it is to outcompete others for space and nutrients. At first sight, this seems to place the evolutionary increase of contingent complexity under tension with natural selection, since greater complexity requires more selection-relevant structure to be physically constructed at each generation. However, bacterial cells are constructed using *parallel* rather than sequential processes. With parallel construction, a cell can become more complex, and therefore larger and more highly structured, without requiring more time to reproduce. Indeed, this is what is observed in nature: the growth rate of populations of bacterial cells increases with cell size

Figure 1: *E. coli* replication time in minutes (left scale) and dry mass in 10^{-15} grams (right scale) as functions of number of ribosomes ($\times 10^3$). All numbers are from Milo and Phillips [2015].

[Bremer and Dennis, 1996]. This would not be possible if bacterial cells did not rely on parallelism at a massive scale.

Ribosomes are macromolecular complexes made of rRNA which translate mRNA into protein, the most fundamental construction process employed by the living cell. A bacterium's replication time decreases as the fraction of its dry mass consisting of rRNA increases. In the limit, a single *E. coli* can contain 7.2×10^4 ribosomes and rRNA can account for fully 37% of its dry mass, achieving a replication time as short as 24 minutes [Milo and Phillips, 2015]. See Figure 1.

All living cells have non-trivial logical depth since they are all many orders of magnitude more massive than their genomes, which function as compressed self-descriptions. Decompression is accomplished by means of gene expression networks, which permit genes to be expressed at variable rates and in numbers far exceeding their representation in absolute numbers in the genome. Although ribosomes are made of rRNA not protein, they are similarly over expressed relative to their representation in the genome. The *E. coli* genome does not have 7.2×10^4 copies of the gene encoding its rRNA; it only has seven [Milo and Phillips, 2015].

Parallelism is not limited to translation of mRNA into protein by ribosomes. It is also used to accelerate duplication of the bacterial genome itself. This process is implemented by a pair of replication forks that copy the circular DNA molecule forming the chromosome of the mother cell, resulting in a $2\times$ speedup. However, at rapid growth rates, replication cycles overlap, so that

additional replication forks initiate before earlier rounds of replication have completed. As a result, multiple replication forks can be active at once and chromosome replication and segregation proceed concurrently across generations, yielding further parallel speedup [Youngren et al., 2014].

Eukaryotic cells exploit parallelism to an even greater extent, by incorporation of complex self-replicating components like mitochondria that reproduce in parallel, and by distribution of their genomes across multiple chromosomes, which are copied and exported in parallel. However, it is indisputable that, with the advent of multicellular organisms, self-replication by means of parallel processes achieved a breakthrough to a qualitatively different level. The existence of organisms as large as elephants and whales would not be remotely possible were it not for the fact that cell division, growth and differentiation are inherently parallel processes.¹

In summary, the study of self-replication by parallel processes is critical to achieving the primary goal of the field of artificial life, the demonstration of open-ended evolution of artificial organisms of increasing complexity. Despite this, and despite a long history of research on artificial self-replicating systems [Sipper, 1998, Freitas and Merkle, 2004], there has been relatively little study of systems that replicate using parallel processes. The prior work relevant to parallel self-replication can be divided into five categories:

1. Artificial organisms that replicate using sequential processes implemented on top of synchronous [von Neumann, 1966, Langton, 1984] or asynchronous parallel substrates [Nehaniv, 2004].
2. Artificial organisms implemented on top of asynchronous parallel substrates that replicate using non-contingent parallelism provided by the substrate [Laing, 1977, Hutton, 2004] instead of parallelism implemented by contingent duplicated structure.
3. Simulations of spatially distributed evolving populations of self-replicating sequential programs [Ray, 1994, Adami et al., 1994].
4. Autocatalytic sets defined in artificial chemistries that are not complete organisms because they do not isolate their reactants and products and/or lack the complexity of complete organisms [Farmer et al., 1986, Nakamura, 2010].
5. Self-replicating parallel programs in shared-memory multiprocessors [Thearling and Ray, 1996].

Of these, the work of Nakamura, Thearling, and Hutton is most relevant to the present paper; because Hutton's work requires more extended treatment, we discuss Nakamura and Thearling immediately below and dedicate a separate section to Hutton.

Nakamura [2010] showed how programs for a universal computer can be encoded as a parallel production system hosted on an asynchronous parallel substrate. He proved important properties of his encoding scheme including freedom from race conditions. It follows that programs which halt yield unique solutions. Finally, he described a parallel asynchronous self-replicating system based on a self-replicating program encoded using his scheme that replicates in time logarithmic in program size. Unfortunately, because no experimental results were described, this speedup can only be considered a theoretical upperbound and an implementation on real parallel hardware would be subject to overhead like non-zero mixing times of reactants and other factors not addressed in the paper.

¹One might consider *eusociality* as practiced by social insects (ants) and some mammals (mole rats) to be a continuation of this pattern.

Thearling and Ray [1996] described evolution of parallel self-replicating programs in a version of Tierra which included a *split* instruction that caused a process to fork into a pair of processes on a shared-memory multiprocessor. Unlike spatial parallelism on a distributed-memory multicomputer, these processes execute in parallel without duplication and distribution of the programs defining the processes. The instruction also modified an index register in a way specific to each daughter process so that the address range was divided between them. The ancestral program was not a *quine*, which replicate using dual *translation* and *copying* processes, but instead copied itself directly by exploiting its residency in random access shared-memory. Nor was it sequential; it contained a single split instruction that reduced execution time by $2\times$ relative to a non-parallel copying program. Although the evolution of programs with reduced execution times was demonstrated, it should be noted that adding n splits would decrease the execution time by $2^n\times$ of *any* program copying a block of memory of size 2^n on this architecture, and the programs which evolved simply added splits while padding with non-operational instructions so that program length remained evenly divisible by 2^n .

The brevity of the above literature review suggests that the topic of parallel self-replication has been severely understudied. The work presented in this paper addresses this gap. We first develop a concurrency-based analysis of the classical von Neumann replicator, treating it as a decomposition of the self-replication problem into subproblems whose execution order is constrained by shared resources and data dependencies. This extended example makes precise the claim that modularity, concurrency, and parallelism together form a system architecture compatible with the evolution of increased complexity. We then show how these ideas can be realized in a combinator-based artificial chemistry based on program fragments, described in detail in Williams [2016] but summarized here as needed for completeness. Next we introduce a compartment mechanism, *roving piles*, which function as a data structure for representing compact, spatially embedded sets of *actors* supporting isolation, reactant concentration, and controlled communication in artificial chemistries. Finally, we describe an artificial cell hosted on roving piles that reproduces using a spatially distributed asynchronous parallel pipeline. By adding extra copies of programs implementing the limiting steps in the pipeline, we demonstrate a speedup regime in which larger artificial cells reproduce in less time than smaller ones.

The claim of this paper is precise: it identifies and instantiates a previously unarticulated mechanism by which increased organizational complexity can become a selective advantage rather than a selective burden through spatial parallelism. Demonstrating open-ended evolution remains a longer-term goal; the contribution here is to show that the architectural precondition for it can be satisfied.

The remainder of the paper develops this claim in three stages. The first, Sections 2–3, is conceptual. Section 2 argues that an evolvable system architecture must support modularity, concurrency and parallelism, and explains why each is necessary. Section 3 makes this abstract thesis concrete by analyzing the von Neumann replicator as a scheduling problem: self-replication is decomposed into subproblems whose execution order is constrained by shared resources and data dependencies, and the analysis identifies precisely which architectural choices enlarge the space of permissible schedules yielding parallel speedup.

The second stage, Sections 4–7, is constructive. Section 4 summarizes the combinator-based artificial chemistry in which the cell is defined. Section 5 describes the six-stage synthesis pipeline and the autocatalytic set it generates. Section 6 introduces roving piles as a compartment device that provides isolation, reactant concentration, and communication without membrane physics. Section 7 shows how roving piles are extended to support parallel export and binary fission without

reintroducing a sequential bottleneck.

The third stage, Sections 8–10, is experimental and analytical. Section 8 describes the complete artificial cell that integrates all of these mechanisms. Section 9 compares the artificial cell with Hutton’s 2D artificial cells, the principal antecedent of the present work. Section 10 reports experimental results demonstrating a speedup regime in which larger cells replicate faster than smaller ones, analyzes those results in terms of a simple scheduling model, and proposes ways in which the architecture could be tested more strongly.

2 Modularity, Concurrency, Parallelism

Since its beginning, the field of artificial life has been concerned with the twin problems of the origin of life on Earth and its evolution into forms of increasing complexity. Because these problems are among the most important in science, the idea that experiments with artificial chemistries, organisms, and ecologies hosted on computers might substitute for direct observation of events from the lost history of the early Earth remains extremely seductive. Still, progress has been slower than many might have expected, and artificial life’s (arguably) most compelling demonstrations are already several decades old. It follows that a new approach is needed. In this section we motivate the approach taken in this paper by arguing that the evolution of increased complexity depends on a system architecture with three essential characteristics: *modularity*, *concurrency*, and *parallelism*.

Phylogenetic reconstructions indicate that all life on Earth descends from a last universal common ancestor (LUCA) that existed as early as 3.8 billion years ago [Glansdorff et al., 2008]. This organism was probably a chemical autotroph living near a geothermal vent. Notwithstanding its likely inability to synthesize amino acids, it was already quite complex, containing an estimated 355 genes. Significantly, like all of its descendants, it possessed the molecular machinery needed to transcribe DNA into RNA, and translate RNA into proteins. Fossil stromatolites show that by 3.7 billion years ago, the tree of life rooted at LUCA had branched many times, yielding a diversity of more complex organisms occupying a range of niches in complex ecologies [Nutman et al., 2016].

Although the mystery of LUCA’s origin is paramount among the open questions in our field, the question of how an organism of LUCA’s non-negligible complexity evolved into a diversity of still more complex forms may be more immediately amenable to investigation using the artificial life approach. In software engineering terms, did LUCA possess a system architecture that facilitated its further evolution? If so, what were the essential characteristics of this architecture? Could an artificial organism with an architecture possessing these same characteristics be designed? Would an artificial organism so designed, placed in an artificial world where it was forced to compete with other organisms of the same kind for resources, evolve into a diverse ecology of still more complex organisms, given enough time? We believe that the answers to the first, third and fourth questions are all ‘yes’ and these beliefs motivate the present work.

2.1 The Cost of Increased Complexity and the Role of Parallelism

It has been proposed that a sustained increase in the complexity of the most complex entities in an evolving population is a hallmark of open-ended evolution [Taylor et al., 2016]. The complexity at issue here is not randomness and not mere duplication, but structure in the self-description that has been shaped by selection—the contingent complexity defined in Section 1. Such structure must be expressed to matter: selection cannot preserve what reproduction does not instantiate, and instantiation is not free. The genome must be copied and translated into phenome in each

reproductive cycle. Both processes incur costs, exposing genome to the universal selection pressure associated with reproduction itself; both are then subject, in addition, to the niche-specific selection pressures associated with ecology. Increased contingent complexity therefore increases the work of reproduction, and that additional work is always subject to selection.

There are circumstances in which this cost can be offset by other means. A parasite that evolves a complex apparatus for host entry may recover the construction cost through the advantage conferred by successful entry. But even when such offsets occur, the result need not be a sustained increase in overall complexity. Indeed, lineages that adopt parasitic strategies often exhibit net reductions in complexity over time [Nakjang et al., 2013] because many previously necessary functions become dispensable in the host environment and are no longer maintained by selection.

Parallelism acts differently. Rather than offsetting the replication-time cost of increased complexity through an ecological payoff, it reduces that cost directly, by spatially distributing the additional reproductive work. Unlike niche-dependent strategies, parallelism does not require a particular ecological context to be effective; it acts on replication time regardless of environment, and it remains applicable even if organisms also exploit niche-specific opportunities. In living systems it is ubiquitous, from the overexpression of ribosomes [Scott et al., 2010, Scott and Hwa, 2011] to the parallel replication forks of rapidly growing bacteria to the hierarchical parallelism of multicellular organisms. It is therefore the most general mechanism by which the cost of increased contingent complexity can be offset, and the only one that operates under the generic competitive conditions under which complexity must accumulate if open-ended evolution is to occur.

2.2 Evolutionary Ratchets and Surplus Capacity

The preceding discussion sharpens a central riddle about open-ended evolution: if increased complexity is generically costly because it increases the work of reproduction, why does the upper bound of complexity continue to rise over evolutionary time? Granted, there are innumerable more simple organisms than complex ones, and organisms as complex as ourselves occupy only the tail of a very broad distribution [Carroll, 2001], yet the question remains: how does the upper bound of complexity continue to increase even while simple organisms remain predominant?

Complexity is generically disadvantageous because it increases replication cost. That explains the predominance of simple organisms. But if complexity is costly, how does it accumulate in lineages such as our own? Under the notion of complexity adopted here, complexity increases through adaptation to ecological contexts. Yet selection pressures change over time, and complexity that was once adaptive may become neutral or even maladaptive when contexts change. So why doesn't complexity *decrease*?

One of the most important routes by which complexity increases is *duplication* followed by *specialization* [Force et al., 1999]. When the resulting specialized structure later becomes entrenched, this sequence functions as an evolutionary *ratchet* [Maynard Smith and Szathmary, 1995], rendering the increase effectively irreversible. In such cases, reversion to the simpler precursor is no longer possible even if the specialization subsequently becomes neutral or maladaptive [Lukeš et al., 2011]. Because the complexity is locked in, and no longer serves a purpose, we call it *vestigial*.

When parallelism yields replication speedup, the resulting replication-time margin is surplus to the organism's minimal requirements. Significantly, this *surplus capacity* can offset the replication-time costs of additional adaptive and vestigial complexity, thereby reducing the selection pressure against both and permitting both to accumulate over time. According to this view, complex organisms are evolutionary palimpsests, with new adaptations written over older structures that remain partly

preserved by entrenchment. They exist primarily because life on Earth is ancient and, generally speaking, survive not solely by virtue of their complexity, but also despite it.²

2.3 Modularity and Evolvability

Artificial organism capable of open-ended evolution must possess an architecture in which both complexity-increasing ratchets and mechanisms that mitigate the costs of increased complexity can be realized. The first essential characteristic of this system architecture is *modularity*. Modularity exists at many levels in the biochemical apparatus of the cell. Protein structural domains, individual proteins, protein complexes and protein interaction networks have all been described as “modules” [Pereira-Leal et al., 2006]. Significantly, there are examples of increased biological complexity originating from the duplication and specialization of modules at each of these levels. Modularity provides the objects—the modules—that can be duplicated, and subsequently specialized, yielding a repertoire of components of increasing complexity.

2.4 Concurrency, Robustness, and the Mitigation of Complexity

If modularity provides the modules that are duplicated and specialized to increase complexity, then concurrency allows them to be composed in ways that mitigate the costs of those increases. Executable modules are *processes* and concurrency is the property of a system that allows processes to be executed in different orders without affecting the result. More precisely, concurrency allows processes to be executed in *partial orders* defined solely by data dependencies. This flexibility increases robustness.³ While the connection between modularity and evolvability has often been emphasized, the importance of concurrency to an evolvable system architecture has not been previously noted. This is probably because concurrent execution is the default for biochemical systems. However, this is not true of computational systems. Indeed, to our knowledge, there is no artificial organism apart from our own that replicates using operations that can be performed in different orders.

A system is *redundant* if it contains multiple instances of the same component and if working instances can substitute for broken instances in the event of failure. Duplication creates multiple process instances and concurrency allows one instance to execute instead of another, yielding redundancy.

A system is *degenerate* if it can solve the same problem in different ways [Edelman and Gally, 2001]. Concurrency supports degeneracy because it allows a process derived by duplication and specialization of an antecedent process to execute instead of the antecedent. Redundancy and degeneracy increase robustness because they allow organisms to survive component failure and respond in a variety of ways to complex environments.

2.5 Parallelism and Fitness: How Complexity Pays for Itself

Concurrency is a necessary precondition for *parallelism*, the simultaneous execution of processes on multiple processors. Absent a global clock, parallelism is impossible without concurrency. Absent parallelism, complex organisms are at a disadvantage relative to simpler organisms in the competition for resources, since they require more time to replicate.

²“That which does not kill us makes us stranger.” — Trevor Goodchild, *Aeon Flux*.

³Robustness’ in the engineering sense, not in the sense it is used in evolutionary biology, where it is generally understood to mean stability of the genotype-to-phenotype mapping.

Figure 2: *Modularity* facilitates increases in complexity by allowing *duplication* and *specialization* of *modules*. *Processes* are executable modules that *concurrency* allows to be executed in different orders. In a concurrent system, duplication of processes can increase *redundancy*, while duplication followed by specialization can increase *degeneracy*. These mitigate the cost of increased complexity by increasing *robustness*. *Parallelism*, the simultaneous execution of processes on multiple processors, mitigates the cost of increased complexity by decreasing the time an artificial organism needs to replicate.

Parallelism mitigates the cost of increased complexity by decreasing replication time. This is the most universal mechanism by which complexity can “pay for itself.” A lineage can accumulate complexity by duplication and specialization of modules, while offsetting the fitness costs of increased complexity by executing the resulting processes in parallel. In biology this is not an exotic phenomenon; it is the norm. The most striking examples include the massive use of ribosomes in parallel protein synthesis, the use of multiple replication forks in genome duplication, and the hierarchical parallelism intrinsic to multicellular life.

In the remainder of the paper we develop this claim in two complementary ways. First, in Section 3 we use the von Neumann replicator as an extended example to make the architecture concrete by analyzing the constraints on execution order imposed by shared resources and data dependencies. This analysis yields a simple but powerful lesson: whether parallel speedup is possible depends on the structure of these constraints, and evolvability depends on whether new modules can be introduced by duplication and specialization while preserving and expanding the available parallelism. Second, in Sections 8–10 we provide an existence proof by describing artificial cells that reproduce using spatially distributed asynchronous parallel processes and showing that larger cells can replicate in less time than smaller ones.

3 The Von Neumann Replicator as a Case Study

This section develops a central claim of the paper: the evolvability of an organismal architecture depends not only on *what* functional components exist, but on the structure of the constraints they impose on execution order. We make this precise using the classical von Neumann replicator, reinterpreted as an asynchronous self-replicating system decomposed into subproblems with explicit shared-resource and data-dependency constraints. The point is not to take this case study too literally, but to use it as an extended example that makes the roles of modularity, concurrency, and parallelism concrete.

3.1 Decomposition and Subproblems

As conceived by von Neumann [1966], a self-replicating system consists of five components

$$A + B + C + D + \phi(A + B + C + D)$$

where A is a *translator*, B is a *copier*, C is a *controller*, D is *payload* and $\phi(A + B + C + D)$ is a *description* of A , B , C and D . Although von Neumann's self-replicating system was formalized as a synchronous cellular automaton, the above schema applies equally well to an asynchronous system of five *actors* which can be viewed as an autocatalytic set in an artificial chemistry governed by two rules:

These rules have reactants on the left side of the arrow and products on the right. The first rule translates the description into a set of *programs* while the second rule copies the description. Each rule describes a *subproblem* which must be solved to achieve self-replication. The reactants and products of subproblems c and d are omitted for the time being, but might (for example) recognize when the a and b subproblems have completed, export products into the daughter cell, and effect fission of an enclosing membrane. For the moment, we assume that the times required to solve c and d are small and, unlike a and b , independent of the length of the description, $\phi(A + B + C + D)$. Nevertheless, $\phi(C)$ and $\phi(D)$ are likely as long as $\phi(A)$ and $\phi(B)$ and (like them) must be both translated and copied.

3.2 Concurrency, Parallelism, and Execution-Order Constraints

In computer science, a *concurrent* system consists of subprocesses that can be executed in different orders, constrained only by *data dependencies*. A data dependency exists when one subprocess provides the input to a second, in which case the first process must complete before the second can begin. *Concurrency* is a necessary precondition for *parallelism*, which is the simultaneous execution of subprocesses on different processors. Parallelism imposes additional constraints on execution order since a resource being used by one subprocess cannot be simultaneously used by another. The shared resource in the self-replication problem is the description, $\phi(A + B + C + D)$. It follows that subproblems a and b cannot be solved in parallel, which we abbreviate as a/b . Since there are no data dependencies, the execution order of the a and b subproblems is otherwise unconstrained, so that $a \rightarrow b$ and $b \rightarrow a$ are both possible.

3.3 Modularizing Descriptions to Expose Parallelism

The asynchronous system can be reformulated so that parallel solution of subproblems is possible by splitting the description into four pieces:

$$A + B + C + D + \phi(A) + \phi(B) + \phi(C) + \phi(D).$$

The system is still governed by two rules

$$\begin{aligned} ax : A + \phi(x) &\rightarrow A + \phi(x) + x \\ bx : B + \phi(x) &\rightarrow B + 2\phi(x) \end{aligned}$$

where fx is program f and description x . However, there are now eight subproblems, which we refer to as aa , ab , ac , ad , ba , bb , bc and bd . Because there are no data dependencies between the subproblems, they can be solved sequentially in any of $8!$ possible orders, including

$$aa \rightarrow ab \rightarrow ac \rightarrow ad \rightarrow ba \rightarrow bb \rightarrow bc \rightarrow bd.$$

To understand the potential for parallel solution of subproblems, the constraints on simultaneous execution imposed by shared resources must first be identified. Execution of a process solving subproblem fx precludes the simultaneous execution of processes solving subproblems fy and gx since there are single instances of program f and description x . This imposes ten constraints on simultaneous execution which we abbreviate as fx/fy and fx/gx . Nevertheless, even with these constraints, many strategies for parallel solution of subproblems remain, including

$$(aa \mid ba) \rightarrow (ab \mid bb) \rightarrow (ac \mid bc) \rightarrow (ad \mid bd)$$

which yields a $2\times$ speedup relative to the sequential strategy. Distributing the description across multiple actors increased parallelism by reducing contention for a shared resource.

3.4 Redundancy/Overexpression and Speedup Regimes

However, splitting the description also creates new opportunities for parallelism that can be exploited by the addition of extra copies of A , B , $\phi(A)$ and $\phi(B)$. Let n be the total number of copies of A , B , $\phi(A)$ and $\phi(B)$ in an asynchronous self-replicating system:

$$n(A + \phi(A) + B + \phi(B)) + C + \phi(C) + D + \phi(D).$$

The system is governed by two rules:

$$\begin{aligned} a_i x_j : A_i + \phi(x_j) &\rightarrow A_i + \phi(x_j) + x_j \\ b_i x_j : B_i + \phi(x_j) &\rightarrow B_i + 2\phi(x_j). \end{aligned}$$

It requires the solution of $4(n+1)$ subproblems $a_i x_j$ and $b_i x_j$ to achieve self-replication. The same constraints on simultaneous execution of the increased number of subproblems apply: fx/fy and fx/gx . When $n=2$, these constraints allow the following strategy (and many others of equivalent or lesser efficiency) for parallel solution:

$$(a_0a_0 \mid a_1a_1 \mid b_0b_0 \mid b_1b_1) \rightarrow (a_0b_0 \mid a_1b_1 \mid b_0a_0 \mid b_1a_1) \rightarrow (a_0c \mid b_0c \mid a_1d \mid b_1d).$$

Because this strategy contains only three steps, the speedup is $\frac{4}{3}\times$ relative to the non-redundant parallel strategy and $\frac{8}{3}\times$ relative to the sequential strategy. This system is the first in a series of systems where additional instances of the actors which translate and copy can offset the replication cost of control and payload actors leading to decreased self-replication time. Speedup occurs because the work of translating and copying the descriptions of the control and payload actors, $\phi(C)$ and

$\phi(D)$, is divided among all instances of the translate and copy actors, A and B .

A hypothetical system containing only translate and copy actors

$$n(A + \phi(A) + B + \phi(B))$$

would not benefit from additional A and B instances, since minimum length strategies for all n require two steps:

$$(a_0a_0 \mid b_0b_0 \mid \dots \mid a_{n-1}a_{n-1} \mid b_{n-1}b_{n-1}) \rightarrow (a_0b_0 \mid b_0a_0 \mid \dots \mid a_{n-1}b_{n-1} \mid b_{n-1}a_{n-1}).$$

3.5 Pipelined Translation and Copying under Data Dependencies

Although the example of the asynchronous von Neumann replicator is compelling, its lack of data dependencies makes it unusually amenable to speedup via parallelism. Indeed, it falls into a category of problems often termed *embarrassingly parallel*. Many problems cannot be decomposed so easily. Although data dependencies do not necessarily preclude parallel speedup, they sometimes allow only a more limited form of parallelism termed *pipeline parallelism*. Consider an asynchronous self-replicating system governed by the following two rules:

$$\begin{aligned} a_ix_j : A_i + \phi(x_j) &\rightarrow A_i + 2\tilde{\phi}(x_j) \\ b_ix_j : B_i + 2\tilde{\phi}(x_j) &\rightarrow B_i + x_j + 2\phi(x_j). \end{aligned}$$

The first rule consumes a description $\phi(x_j)$ and produces a pair of *reversed* descriptions $2\tilde{\phi}(x_j)$. The second rule consumes a pair of reversed descriptions and produces a program x_j and two descriptions $2\phi(x_j)$. In effect, the second rule simultaneously translates and copies. Although this process might seem contrived, it is very natural when programs are represented as *list zippers* [Huet, 1997] (Section 5.1) because the zipper's *back* is already a reversed sequence, so reversal is the structurally inevitable intermediate step when copying proceeds by reading off one end and writing onto another. Moreover, it is precisely the process used by the artificial cell described in this paper.

A self-replicating system using this process for translation and copying contains four data dependencies not present in the embarrassingly parallel system. These can be abbreviated as $bx > ax$, since for all x subproblem bx cannot be solved before subproblem ax has completed. Despite these constraints, for $n = 2$, the following strategy is possible

$$(a_0a_0 \mid a_1a_1) \rightarrow (a_0b_0 \mid a_1b_1 \mid b_0a_0 \mid b_1a_1) \rightarrow (b_0b_0 \mid b_1b_1 \mid a_0c \mid a_1d) \rightarrow (b_0c \mid b_1d).$$

This strategy yields a $2\times$ speedup relative to the sequential strategy. Although not quite as large as the $\frac{8}{3}\times$ speedup observed in the embarrassingly parallel system, the speedup in the parallel pipelined system is still significant.

3.6 Export Constraints and the Organization Bottleneck

The von Neumann decomposition assigns the organizational work of replication to the controller C together with whatever mechanism transfers completed products from mother to daughter. A simple toy abstraction of this transfer process is to introduce ($m \geq 1$) instances of a program E that export the products of the mother's translation and copying processes:

$$n(A + \phi(A) + B + \phi(B)) + C + \phi(C) + D + \phi(D) + m(E + \phi(E)).$$

The corresponding export rule is

$$e_i x_j : E_i + x_j + \phi(x_j) \rightarrow E_i + x'_j + \phi(x'_j)',$$

where x'_j and $\phi(x'_j)'$ denote a program and its description after export to the daughter.

This abstraction is useful because it makes the organizational problem explicit, but it should be read only as a toy model. Its purpose is not to characterize the final architecture developed later, but to isolate the bottleneck created when daughter construction depends on a distinct export process.

Because export can occur only after both members of a program-description pair have been completed, execution order must satisfy the additional precedence constraints

$$e x > a x, \quad e x > b x.$$

Here $p > q$ means that completion of subproblem p is constrained to occur after completion of subproblem q . Export therefore introduces new dependencies on top of those already present in the pipelined system of Section 3.5.

In this toy formulation, one is naturally led to ask whether increasing the number m of exporter instances can remove the resulting export bottleneck. That question is intentionally naive. It treats export as though it were a separate task carried out by a bank of dedicated exporter programs. The deeper problem, however, is not merely the number of exporters, it is their coordination. Critically, daughter construction seems to require a dedicated control mechanism to certify that the daughter has received the required complement of components.

In the classical von Neumann picture, this channel is effectively sequential: the daughter is organized by a process that places or certifies components one site at a time. As a result, the architecture can appear highly parallel at the level of functional decomposition while still retaining a sequential bottleneck at the level of daughter organization. The question taken up in Section 7 is therefore not simply whether additional exporter instances can increase throughput. It is whether the organizational work of export can be distributed so that daughter construction is genuinely parallel rather than only superficially so.

3.7 Why Execution-Order Constraints Matter for Evolvable Architecture

Because the von Neumann self-replicator is the canonical example of a self-replicating system, and because his problem decomposition is universal and its notation familiar, we used it to show that self-replication decomposes into subproblems whose execution order is constrained by shared resources and data dependencies. These constraints determine both (i) the amount of concurrency available, and (ii) whether or not that concurrency can be converted into parallel speedup. This is why execution-order constraints are central to evolvable architecture.

The connection to Section 2 is direct. Modularity supplies the units that can be duplicated and specialized. Concurrency allows those executable modules (processes) to be composed flexibly, yielding redundancy and degeneracy, and therefore robustness. Parallelism mitigates the cost of increased complexity by decreasing replication time. The von Neumann case study makes the central lesson operational: increasing complexity by duplication and specialization increases the number of subproblems that must be solved during replication, but the net effect on fitness depends on whether the resulting execution-order constraints preserve concurrency and permit parallel speedup. In the sections that follow we show how these architectural principles can be realized in an artificial

chemistry, and how they can be embodied in artificial cells that replicate by spatially distributed asynchronous parallel processes.

4 Object-Oriented Combinator Chemistry

The artificial cells described in this paper are defined in Object-Oriented Combinator Chemistry (OCC), introduced in Williams [2016]. This section summarizes the subset of OCC needed to follow the cell construction and experiments, with emphasis on the design constraints that motivated its architecture.

4.1 Abstract and Concrete Machines

Machines exist along a continuum from abstract to concrete. At the abstract end sit *random access stored program (RASP) computers* [Cook and Reckhow, 1973], models that are powerful precisely because they abstract away the physical costs of computation in space (communication is global and any memory location is readable/writeable at unit cost) and time (a global clock makes synchronization free). At the concrete end sit *asynchronous cellular automata (ACA)*, which are finite state, embedded in space, communicate locally, and forgo a global clock [Nakamura, 1974, Berman and Simon, 1988]. For the purposes of this paper, a machine is concrete when it can be $O(1)$ -reduced to an ACA [Williams, 2016].

The distinction matters here because the central claim of this paper is only meaningful if replication time is physically grounded. In an abstract machine, unconstrained by realizable physics, computation time has no connection to physical time and can serve as neither a proxy for reproductive fitness nor as a measure of complexity. Facts about the replication times of abstract self-replicating systems cannot license conclusions about living cells, which are concrete machines. Reduction to an ACA substrate is what closes this gap.

4.2 Biochemistry as Information Processing

An *artificial chemistry* is a dynamical system of constructible objects [Fontana and Buss, 1996]. When an artificial chemistry is implemented on top of an ACA its abstract constructions are *reified*. Its atoms have mass and location, all interactions are local, and mixing is not statistical but a function of individual motions and distances travelled. Under reification, the abstract and physical constructions do not merely coincide; the distinction between them dissolves. If the ACA itself is embedded in the physical world so that its spatial and temporal dimensions are coextensive with physical space and time, it becomes difficult to distinguish such a system from a real physical process.

Ordinary chemistry is stoichiometric: reactions depend on concentrations and individual molecules are interchangeable instances of a type. Biochemistry is different in kind: information-carrying molecules such as DNA may be present in quantities as small as a single instance, and the specific information they encode, not their concentration, determines their roles in the reactions they participate in [Watson and Crick, 1953]. A single molecule can determine the entire reaction; what matters is what is encoded, not how much is present. It means that biochemistry cannot be adequately described in purely statistical terms — an explanation in terms of information and computation is literally demanded.

Functional programming languages share this deeper organizational property. What matters is not merely that complex objects can be assembled from simple ones, but that descriptions of behavior

can themselves be represented as objects, constructed from simpler parts, and executed. This is the crucial point of contact with biochemistry. In biochemical systems, informational macromolecules do not merely persist as inert records: the stored information encodes specific functional effects. Moreover, that information can be copied, transformed, and interpreted by other molecular machinery. In functional systems, programs are likewise first-class entities: they can be built compositionally, manipulated as data, and yield effects by execution. After reification on an ACA substrate, this organization becomes physical. How this makes non-trivial self-replication possible is the subject of the following subsection.

4.3 Semantic Closure

A system has *semantic closure* [Pattee, 1995] when the processes that interpret its descriptions are themselves described within the system and subject to its laws. Pattee’s central point is that a living system requires both symbolic and material modes of description, and that these must be linked internally: the symbols must be interpreted by the very machinery whose construction they help direct. In the living cell, the canonical example, the genome encodes the enzymes that replicate and transcribe it, and those enzymes are themselves products of transcription and translation. Nothing external to the cell is required to interpret its own description.

Semantic closure is therefore what separates trivial self-replicators from non-trivial ones. Without it, the organization required to interpret the system’s description resides in the physics, external, non-contingent, and invisible to selection, rather than in the description itself. Achieving semantic closure in a self-replicating system is thus, in effect, the transfer of causal organization from the non-contingent structure of the environment into the contingent structure of the organism. This point is critical for open-ended evolution. The more completely this transfer is achieved, the greater the fraction of the system’s organization that is represented by information subject to selection, and hence the greater the scope for the evolutionary growth of complexity.

Prior artificial chemistries defined constructible objects and composition mechanisms, but the rules governing reactions were specified externally, as laws of physics rather than as objects in the world. Ackley [2013] recognized that an artificial chemistry could serve as an interface to an ACA substrate, a *bespoke physics* that gives its dynamics a physically realizable foundation, but as in prior artificial chemistries, the reaction rules in the systems he described remained external to the chemistry itself. OOCC goes further: by making the atoms of the chemistry *combinators* — program fragments — the rules governing reactions are themselves constructible objects within the system, present in the same world and subject to the same physics. How this is accomplished is described in the sections that follow. Without it, the organization required to interpret the system’s descriptions resides in the physics rather than in the organism, and the complexity of the cell — however elaborate — remains non-contingent and invisible to selection. In summary, OOCC brings together the elements minimally necessary to achieve the results described in this paper: an artificial chemistry concretely grounded in physics whose constructible objects are computer programs.

4.4 Actors

The basic entities in OOCC are called *actors* [Hewitt et al., 1973]. There are three kinds of actors: *methods*, *primitives*, and *composites*. Methods are executable programs and composites are inert

descriptions composed of primitives.⁴ Every actor has a *mass*; primitives have unit mass, while the mass of a composite or method is the number of primitives it contains. In this sense, mass and information are two aspects of the same thing. Mass is the common currency of physical cost accounting in OOC, and this cost accounting takes three forms. The first is material cost: because actors can neither be created nor destroyed, mass is conserved throughout all interactions, and because primitives are typed and types are not fungible, the material cost of self-replication cannot be evaded. The second is transport cost: diffusion is the sole transport mechanism and diffusion rate decreases with mass, so composites move more slowly than the primitives from which they are composed, reflecting the real cost of copying information in the underlying substrate. The third is computation cost: methods are charged for every primitive operation executed, so the mass of what is constructed is a lower bound on the time required to construct it.

Actors are assigned positions in a two-dimensional grid. Multiple actors may reside at a single site. Actors can belong to *groups*. Actors in the same group diffuse as a unit; a group’s diffusion rate decreases with its mass and the mass of a group is the sum of the masses of the actors which comprise it. Methods in the same group execute concurrently (in any order) but not in parallel (simultaneously). This contrasts with methods in different groups, which can execute in parallel. This distinction is essential to the results of the paper. It means that parallel speedup is possible only when computation is spatially distributed. Its benefits cannot be obtained without accepting the corresponding burdens of distributed computation: communication, synchronization, transport, and the coordination of partially independent subtasks. Meeting those burdens requires additional organizational machinery, and therefore additional complexity.

Actors can be linked by three kinds of *bonds*: undirected *hand* bonds, and directed *prev* and *next* bonds (which are inverses of each other). Each actor possesses at most one bond of each kind. Bonds constrain diffusion so that bonded actors must remain in each others’ neighborhoods.

Because all operations are locally defined, programs reference other actors by searching within their neighborhood (or by searching within the neighborhoods of actors to which they are joined by bonds) rather than using global identifiers or addresses. The mechanism by which this search is implemented is described in the following subsection.

4.5 Combinators, Pattern Matching, and the Stack Machine

To make self-replication physically realistic and achieve semantic closure, both programs x and their descriptions $\phi(x)$ must be built from components that are themselves actors and these actors must be subject to mass conservation and diffusion. The building blocks of programs and descriptions are combinators of a small number of fixed types. Combinators lack operands, including the target addresses of jumps and function calls needed to implement loops and recursion in programs for RASP computers. It follows that programs composed of combinators, like polypeptides, are topologically simple linear sequences. It is this simplicity that makes them representable as list zippers and copyable by the synthesis pipeline of Section 5.

Combinators form a hierarchy: primitives each implement a single operation; primitives compose into composites; and composites, after unquoting, become executable methods. To give all combinators a uniform type signature, they are defined as transformations of a *nondeterministic stack machine* [Williams, 2016]. The machine state is a stack whose elements are *sets of actors*. A

⁴OOC also defines a fourth kind, *objects*, which serve as containers for other actors, and are the source of the “object-oriented” in the artificial chemistry’s name, but are not used by the artificial cell described here.

combinator pops one or two sets from the top of the stack, computes a result, and pushes a new set back.

A *monad* is a data type for values with computational effects [Moggi, 1991, Wadler, 1990]. Programs comprised of fragments which return this type sequence these effects. Programs can be composed with the Kleisli operator (\gg) and applied to values with the bind operator ($\gg=$). The operational semantics of the stack machine derive from its monadic type, and the computational effects of this type are what make non-deterministic search possible; they are developed in Section 4.8.

Instead of referencing actors using addresses, a method searches its spatial neighborhood for actors satisfying a set of preconditions. Nondeterministic choice is the mechanism by which this search is implemented. `amb` takes a set of actors $\{x_1, \dots, x_n\}$ on top of the stack and *forks* the computation, producing one branch for each element [McCarthy, 1963]. Each branch continues independently with a singleton $\{x_i\}$ on top of the stack. A branch fails when `amb` is applied to an empty value `{}`. Branches which fail are pruned; the computation succeeds on the first surviving branch. If all branches fail, the method fails without side effects. Although programs cannot address actors by their positions, they can locate them by type and structural properties in their neighborhoods — which is precisely the mechanism available to molecular machines operating in a chemical soup, and is partly what gives the chemistry its claim to physical realism. ⁵

4.6 Spock: Notation and Transactional Convention

Programs are written in a language called *Spock*, a domain specific language with a Haskell-like syntax that compiles to sequences of primitive combinators [Williams, 2016]. Spock is syntactic sugar for human readability only. The compiler is a straightforward translation; after compilation, Spock’s syntax is entirely irrelevant — OOC and the simulation operate exclusively on combinator sequences. A Spock program and its compiled combinator sequence are the same object viewed at different levels of notation: there is no Spock runtime, no separate interpretation step, and no semantic content in Spock that is not already present in the combinators themselves. Named bindings (`x <- ...`) compile to writes into a small symbol table threaded through the computation; later references to `x` compile to reads from that table. No heap is required. Data flows right-to-left within a line, with `=<<` playing the role of function application: `f =<< g =<< h m` means apply `h` to `m`, then `g` to the result, then `f`.

To make these mechanics concrete, consider a simple method written in Spock that searches the neighborhood for an ungrouped primitive with a hand bond. If it succeeds, the executing actor joins the ungrouped primitive’s group:

```
p <- amb =<< primitive =<< ungrouped =<< neighbors m;  
some =<< hands p;  
join p m
```

Primitive combinators are of four types: *generators*, *filters*, *guards*, and *actions*. The special generator `m` (short for `me`) seeds every computation by pushing the executing actor itself; all other generators pop an actor from the top of the stack and push a related set in its place. The generator `neighbors` returns the set of actors found in the Moore neighborhood of `m`. These are filtered by the `ungrouped` and `primitive` combinators, so that only actors in singleton groups of primitive type survive as

⁵The Stringmol artificial chemistry [Hickinbotham et al., 2016] employs an analogous pattern-based location mechanism: binding sites are identified by Smith-Waterman complementary alignment [Smith and Waterman, 1981] rather than by numeric address.

inputs to the guard `amb`. `amb` forks the computation, binding each of its inputs to `p` in turn. The guard `some` on the second line tests whether `p` has a hand bond; if it does not, that branch is pruned and the computation backtracks to try the next candidate `p`. The action `join` on the third line is committed only on the first branch for which the guard succeeds. If no ungrouped primitive with a hand bond exists in the neighborhood, all branches are pruned and the method fails with no side effects.

Spock supports but does not enforce transactional semantics. The convention observed throughout this paper is that all generators, filters, and guards appear before any actions, so that a method either finds all its preconditions satisfied and commits all its effects atomically, or fails cleanly with no side effects. Nothing in Spock prevents a programmer from mixing guards and actions or omitting necessary preconditions, but doing so would violate this convention and could leave the world in an inconsistent state. The artificial cell described in this paper is constructed entirely from methods that observe this convention. This disciplined use of transactional semantics is what makes methods robust to asynchrony: if two methods attempt to operate on the same structure simultaneously, at most one will find all its guards satisfied; the other will fail cleanly and retry.

4.7 Simulation Dynamics

The simulation dynamics ground the cost accounting used in the experiments of Section 10. They are governed by the Gillespie algorithm [Gillespie, 1977], the standard method for exact stochastic simulation of coupled chemical reactions. There is no time step.

Instead, the priority queue maintains events of three kinds: *diffuse*, *action*, and *request*. When an event reaches the front of the queue it is dispatched according to its type. A *diffuse* event moves a group to an adjacent site. An *action* event selects a method at random from among the group's actors and runs it. A *request* event imports an actor of a specific primitive type into the *roving pile* data structure described in Section 6.6. After an event completes, the group is reinserted into the queue at a time equal to the current time plus the time consumed by servicing the event. To permit this, methods are instrumented to report the time they consume, charging for every primitive operation executed on every branch of the nondeterministic computation until one succeeds at which point the group containing the method is reinserted into the queue at a position reflecting this cost. Diffuse events are scheduled at times proportional to the product of the group's mass and the distance moved, so that heavier groups — those containing more compositional information — diffuse more slowly by virtue of being selected less frequently. This single mechanism therefore grounds both the cost of computation and the cost of data transport in the same physically principled accounting: the operation counts reported in Section 10 are not wall-clock measurements but cumulative charges paid by the simulation at the rate the underlying ACA substrate would impose.

4.8 Program Fragments, Composition, and Monotone Progress

The primitive combinators of Section 4.5 are program fragments in the monadic sense: self-contained units of computation that can be composed into larger fragments and applied to values. Because Kleisli composition ($>=>$) is the sole structuring mechanism in OOC, and because the uniform stack machine interface makes it well-typed and associative, a method is simply a linear sequence of fragments with no privileged internal structure. The absence of operands and addresses, together with the threaded symbol table that handles all named bindings, ensures that programs have no internal cross-references that would force a more complex topology. A sequence suffices. This is why

programs in OCCC can be represented as list zippers and copied by the synthesis pipeline described in Section 5.

This simple program topology suffices for two reasons. The first is the monadic type of the combinators and the second is the simulation dynamics.

The first reason is that the monadic type handles non-determinism implicitly. When a guard fails, the computation backtracks. Significantly, this requires no explicit branching in the program. What would require conditional statements, loops, and/or recursion in a conventional language is implicit in the monadic type. Programs can therefore be linear sequences of combinators because types do much of the work that would otherwise require more complex program topologies.

The second reason is that the simulation dynamics make computations progress monotonically without requiring programs to encode iteration or sequencing between method invocations. Each method, when it fires, commits a set of irreversible changes to persistent state — modifying bonds, group membership, and actor states — and leaves the world in a new conformation. Because state changes are irreversible and conformations are specific, a new conformation satisfies the preconditions of the next method in the pipeline and no others. The Gillespie event loop then drives the computation forward automatically: the next method fires when its preconditions are met, without any program needing to invoke it explicitly. Progress through the pipeline is therefore a consequence of the simulation dynamics rather than of control flow encoded in the programs themselves. The programs are stateless with respect to their own progress; the state *is* the conformation of the world. This is the computational analog of enzyme cascades in living cells: no enzyme encodes knowledge of what comes next, yet the cascade proceeds because the product of each reaction is the substrate of the next.

Together these two properties mean that a linear sequence of combinators, represented as a list zipper, is all that is needed to represent and copy a program in OCCC. The synthesis pipeline of Section 5 depends on both: the monadic type ensures that each stage (and each step within stages requiring multiple steps) executes correctly as a transaction, while the simulation dynamics ensure that stages (and steps) succeed one another without explicit coordination. The connection to Section 3 is direct: the execution-order constraints that determine the space of legal replication schedules are enforced not by a global scheduler but by the local, irreversible state changes that drive monotone progress through the pipeline.

4.9 Generators, Filters, Guards, and Actions

The four combinator types play different roles in the non-deterministic computation: *generators* and *filters* shape the sets that non-determinism branches over; *guards* allow branches to continue or fail; and the separation of guards from *actions* enforces the transactional semantics described in Section 4.6.

Generators return sets of actors which belong to groups or inhabit neighborhoods: **members** pushes the set of all actors in a given actor’s group; **others** pushes the set of all group members except the given actor; **neighbors** pushes the set of actors in the Moore neighborhood of a given actor. Bond generators traverse bond structure: **hands**, **prevs**, and **nexts** pushes the sets of actors joined to a given actor by bonds of those respective types.

Filters refine sets by retaining actors that satisfy a given condition and removing actors that do not. Type filters retain actors of a named type: **primitive**, **composite**, **combinator**, **method**. State filters retain actors satisfying a structural condition: **unbonded** retains actors with no bonds; **ungrouped** retains actors in singleton groups; **handless** retains actors with no hand bond; **similar**

retains actors from its first argument whose type matches any actor found in its second argument. Generators and filters compose freely to address specific sets: `similar n =<< primitive =<< nexts c` pushes the set of primitives bonded via `next` to `c` whose type matches `n`.

Guards test properties of the sets shaped by generators and filters. Where generators and filters determine *what* is present, guards determine *whether* a condition is satisfied. `some` fails if a set is empty; `none` fails if it is nonempty; `implies` fails if the first set is nonempty and the second is empty. A failed guard eliminates the current branch of the computation entirely, leaving the world unchanged on that branch. If all branches are eliminated, the method fails with no side effects.

Actions form the right-hand side of a rule. They modify the persistent state of the world and are committed only after all generators, filters, and guards have completed without failure, making each method a single atomic transaction under the convention described in Section 4.6. `grab` creates a hand bond between two actors. `makePrev` and `makeNext` create directed bonds. `drop`, `deletePrev`, and `deleteNext` remove bonds. `compose` forms a composite from two actors under ($>=>$). `decompose` splits a composite into its two components. `join` moves an actor into a group. `quit` removes an actor from its group and places it in a new singleton group. `unquote` promotes a composite to an executable method.

5 The Synthesis Pipeline and Autocatalytic Set

The zipper [Huet, 1997] is among the most important ideas in functional data structures: by splitting a sequence into a reversed front, a focus, and a back, it provides a cursor that can traverse and modify a sequence using only local operations at its two ends, with no interior addressing. The same trick appears, implicitly, in the Stringmol artificial chemistry described by Hickinbotham et al. [2016]: copying is mediated by a pair of pointer registers advancing through a pair of bound strings that together constitute an implicit zipper. The central mechanism of replication used by the artificial cell described in this paper is similar in its use of a zipper representation but distinct in other respects: a six-stage pipeline that simultaneously synthesizes a program x and copies its zipper representation $\phi(x)$ in a single cycle. This section describes this pipeline in full and shows how it gives rise to an autocatalytic set when supplied with zipper representations of its own programs.

5.1 Zipper Representations of Programs

A program in OOC is physically represented as a *zipper* [Huet, 1997]: a data structure that splits a sequence into a *front* (the portion already traversed, stored in reverse order), a *focus* (the current element), and a *back* (the portion yet to be traversed). In the OOC reification, a next bond connects the back to the front and a hand bond connects the back to its focus. The two-ended interface of the zipper confines all access to the ends of the front and back chains: no actor can reach an interior position by address, enforcing the locality discipline that is a primary design constraint of OOC.

A program's simplest assembly sequence builds it by adding one primitive at a time via Kleisli composition — a right fold with ($>=>$). Both the back and the front of the zipper are composites, with the primitives comprising the front stored in reverse order. The focus is a single primitive between them.

We write $\phi(x)$ for the zipper representation of program x , and $\tilde{\phi}(x)$ for its reversal. The synthesis pipeline takes $\phi(x)$ as input and produces, in a single cycle, both a method enzyme x' (the executable

Figure 3: Six stage parallel pipeline for translating and copying zipper representation of description $\phi(x)$ showing changes to zipper conformation effected by programs A – F . Unlike the pipeline described in Williams [2019], this pipeline produces both program x and description $\phi(x)$ in a single cycle. This permits export to be implemented as a parallel process.

program, ready to be placed in the daughter) and a daughter zipper $\phi(x)'$ (a fresh copy of the description, ready for the daughter to use in the next generation).

5.2 The Six-Stage Pipeline

The pipeline is implemented by six methods A – F ; see Figure 3. Its input is a zipper $\phi(x)$ in the starting conformation: a composite back with a primitive focus at its hand bond and a single-primitive front at its prev bond, and no daughter front. Its output, produced in a single cycle, is a method enzyme x' and a restored mother zipper $\phi(x)$ together with a daughter zipper $\phi(x)'$, both in the starting conformation.

The pipeline proceeds in two passes over the zipper: a forward traversal (stages A – C) that reverses both the mother and a nascent daughter copy, followed by a reverse traversal (stages D – F) that restores both to the starting conformation while simultaneously producing the method enzyme. Figure 3 shows the zipper conformation at each stage transition.

- **A** initiates the forward traversal. It finds a zipper $\phi(x)$ in the starting conformation: a composite back with a primitive focus at its hand bond, a single-primitive mother front at its prev bond, and no daughter front. It recruits a free primitive from the neighborhood whose type matches the focus, and establishes this primitive as the first element of the daughter front via a prev bond. After A , the zipper carries paired fronts of length one and is ready for traversal by B .
- **B** performs each step of the forward traversal. At each activation it finds a composite c whose group contains no other method, confirming it is not already being handled, and whose bonds

exhibit the mid-traversal conformation: a primitive focus at the hand, a mother front at the prev, and a daughter front at the next. It then extends *both* fronts by one element of the same type: the mother front receives a freshly recruited primitive matching the focus, while the daughter front receives the focus actor itself, released by **drop**. Finally it advances the zipper: **decompose** splits the back composite and **grab** installs the recovered primitive as the new focus. After k activations of B, both fronts contain the same reversed prefix $\tilde{\phi}(x_{1..k})$: the mother has been reconstituted from fresh raw materials while the daughter holds the mother’s original actors.

- **C** performs the terminal step of the forward traversal. It recognizes the conformation in which the back is a single primitive (not a composite), confirming the traversal is complete, and adds the final element to both fronts without advancing. The zipper is now focusless with both fronts holding the complete reversed description $\tilde{\phi}(x)$.
- **D** initiates the reverse traversal. It finds the focusless zipper — a primitive back with no focus and a pair of complete fronts — and recruits a matching free primitive, joining it to the back to form a pair of backs. The zipper is now ready for the reverse pass by E.
- **E** performs each step of the reverse traversal. At each activation it finds a group with a pair of backs and a pair of fronts, and simultaneously advances both: **decompose** recovers the leading element from each front and **compose** pushes it onto the corresponding back, growing both backs while shrinking both fronts. After k activations of E, both backs hold the prefix $\phi(x_{1..k})$ in correct order. When the fronts are exhausted, the mother back holds the fully restored $\phi(x)$ and the daughter back holds a complete copy $\phi(x)'$, both ready for F.
- **F** completes the cycle and produces the output. From the mother back it reconstructs the mother zipper $\phi(x)$ in the starting conformation, restoring the pipeline’s input for the next generation. From the daughter back it simultaneously produces two outputs: **unquote** promotes the daughter back directly to a method enzyme x' , and the remaining daughter back material is reassembled into a fresh daughter zipper $\phi(x)'$ in the starting conformation. The single cycle thus yields $x' + \phi(x)'$: an executable enzyme and a description ready for the next synthesis cycle, as shown at the center of Figure 3. Finally, F marks the mother zipper *open*, causing it to migrate to the septum (see Section 7).

The time required for a complete synthesis cycle is dominated by stages B and E, each of which requires a number of activations proportional to the length $|\phi(x)|$ of the program description. All other stages require a constant number of activations. This is what makes B and E the natural targets for redundancy in the parallel cell: supplying n copies of B and E reduces the expected waiting time for each traversal step by a factor of n , without requiring any change to stages A, C, D, or F.

5.3 The Autocatalytic Set

The pipeline A–F synthesizes a method enzyme x' and a daughter zipper $\phi(x)'$ from any zipper $\phi(x)$ it encounters in the pile. An immediate consequence follows from this generality. A–F are themselves programs and therefore have zipper representations $\phi(\text{A})$ – $\phi(\text{F})$. If these zippers are placed in the pile together with A–F themselves, then the pipeline will encounter them and synthesize fresh copies of A–F together with fresh copies of $\phi(\text{A})$ – $\phi(\text{F})$. The set is therefore closed under its own synthesis

operation: the twelve entities — six methods and six zippers — form an *autocatalytic set* [Farmer et al., 1986]: the methods use the zippers to produce additional copies of both methods and zippers, maintaining and amplifying their own population without external intervention. Methods and zippers are the spatially distributed, modular, concurrent, and parallel components of a self-replicating system.

However, the autocatalytic set is not yet a *bona fide* artificial organism. It does not segregate its components from those of other systems: methods and zippers diffuse freely in the world and mix with any other actors present. Absent compartmentalization, the autocatalytic set cannot maintain an identity across time, cannot accumulate heritable variation, and cannot support Darwinian evolution. The compartment mechanism that addresses this is the subject of Section 6.

6 Roving Piles: A Spatial Compartment Data Structure for OCC

6.1 Compartments without Membrane Physics

After elemental building blocks, reaction catalysts, and molecules for storing energy and information, compartments are probably the next most important ingredient in the recipe for life. Given their amazing utility, it is remarkable that, in our universe, we basically get them for free. This is due to the existence of lipid compounds that, when placed in water, spontaneously assemble into *liposomes*, vessels defined by bilayer membranes.

Yet membranes are not uncomplicated. Consider the problem of how to make one grow. To insert a molecule into a lipid bilayer, a set of forces must be applied on the lipid molecules adjacent to the point of insertion to create a gap and these forces must propagate through the bilayer. They must be combined with the attractive forces the lipids exert on each other and the forces exerted on the membrane by the cytoplasm. This *mass spring system* requires a physics far more complex than the rudimentary one underpinning our artificial chemistry, which has no analog of force.

However, there is a still harder problem associated with growth. In order for a cell to grow, two different actions must be coordinated. First, the volume must increase. This can be done by adding something to the cytoplasm. Yet if pressure is to remain constant, the membrane must also increase in area. Complicating matters, the cytoplasm’s volume and the membrane’s area must increase at different rates. Assuming a spherical cell, an increase in the volume by ΔV requires a corresponding increase in surface area by

$$\Delta A = \pi(r^3 + \Delta V)^{\frac{2}{3}} - \pi r^2$$

which depends on the cell’s radius, r . Given the dependence on r , it follows that there is no single local operation that can maintain constant pressure by pairing imports to both cytoplasm and membrane.

Fortunately, membranes are not the only way to achieve the compartmentalization necessary for the creation of life. In fact, in the physical universe, a thing as simple as a water droplet in oil can function as a compartment.⁶ In a computational universe, a compartment is simply a data structure for representing a compact, spatially embedded set. Using a Jordan curve to represent membership in such a set by partitioning space into two disjoint regions, one (*inside*) containing the set’s elements, the other (*outside*) containing everything else, is merely one possibility.

⁶Sokolova et al. [2013] have demonstrated transcription and translation in *E. coli* lysate contained in water-in-oil droplets.

The point is not that membrane physics is unimportant in biology. Rather, it is that the key role played by membranes at the level of system architecture can be captured without committing to a detailed analog of lipid mechanics. For the purposes of artificial life, what compartments provide is an interface: they isolate internal dynamics from the outside world while still permitting controlled exchange of matter and information. In an artificial chemistry, this has three immediate consequences.

First, compartments define a unit of *membership*. They make it meaningful to speak of an organism as a coherent set of reactants and products. Second, by restricting mixing, they permit *concentration* of catalysts and substrates, increasing the rate at which successive pipeline stages find their reactants, and decreasing the time required for multistep synthesis pipelines to complete. Third, compartments provide a controlled medium for *communication* and *transport*: they make it possible to export products, import primitives, and coordinate distributed processes without relying on global addressing or non-local rules.

In the section that follows we describe a concrete data structure for compartments satisfying these requirements in a spatially distributed asynchronous substrate. The device, called a *roving pile*, yields compartments that move, grow, and support parallel computation while remaining implementable using purely local rules.

6.2 Roving Piles: Mechanics

The artificial cells described in this paper are hosted in *roving piles*, a compartment device for OCCC that provides (i) isolation of internal actors from the outside world, (ii) concentration of catalysts and substrates by restricting mixing, and (iii) controlled communication and transport across selectively permeable boundaries. The essential design constraint is that roving piles must be implementable on an asynchronous cellular automaton (ACA) substrate using *purely local rules*. This section gives a definitive description of roving piles as a spatial data structure, together with the primitive combinators that provide the interface needed by programs in the chemistry.

6.3 Groups, Links, Footprints, and Boundaries

North, *east*, *south* and *west* are new relations in OCCC on sets of actors, or *groups*. We will call the edges of group relations, *links*, to distinguish them from the edges of actor relations, which we call *bonds*. As with actors and bonds, groups can possess at most one link of each type. *East* and *west* are inverse relations, *i.e.* $E(x, y) = W(y, x)$; the same is true of *north* and *south*. Because they correspond to the four cardinal compass directions, links of these four types are called *cardinal links*. Cardinal links are used to connect *base groups*.

Up and *down* are a second inverse relation on groups that can be used to represent a stack of additional groups above any base group. A base group is a group without a *down* link; a base group without an *up* link is said to be *uncovered*.

A *roving pile* is a connected component of base groups embedded in the 2D lattice together with the groups contained in stacks above them. The set of base groups form the pile's *footprint* and base groups with one or more empty cardinal links form its *boundary*.

In OCCC, methods in the same stack execute concurrently but not in parallel; they compete for a shared processor resource in zero sum fashion. However, methods in different stacks in the same pile execute in parallel. So that piles can move and grow, and so that actors within piles can freely mix, groups in piles are subject to three primitive operations described below.

Figure 4: Even though it would not split the pile’s footprint, an uncovered base group at P cannot join the stack to its east because this cannot be determined by local analysis alone (left). In contrast, an uncovered base group at Q can do so because it would not split the subset of the footprint within its Moore neighborhood (red). Although a covered base group at A can advance the footprint east (and C is in the footprint) no link to C will be created (middle). In contrast, because there is a path between X and Z in the subset of the footprint contained in the Moore neighborhood of Y (blue), a covered base group at X can advance the footprint east and create a link to the base group at Z. Because the evolution of roving pile shape is governed solely by local rules, pile footprints can overlap (right). However, actors in overlapping neighborhoods cannot interact.

6.4 Diffusion, Retreat, and Advance

Roving pile dynamics are governed by the following three operations:

1. *Diffusion*. A non-base group can be moved to an adjacent stack.
2. *Retreat*. An uncovered base group on the boundary can be moved to an adjacent stack if its removal from the footprint will not split the footprint into separate connected components.
3. *Advance*. A covered base group on the boundary can be replaced in the footprint by the group above it and used to extend the footprint in the direction of an empty cardinal link.

Ideally, these operations would be implemented as described above and performed at random. Unfortunately, the retreat and advance operations, as described, cannot be implemented using only local rules.

6.5 Locality Constraints and Moore-Neighborhood Tests

Determining whether or not the removal of a group from the footprint will split the footprint into separate connected components is inconsistent with an implementation on an ACA substrate since it is a function of non-local properties of the cardinal link relation. For example, the footprint might consist of base groups forming a square with sides one group wide and n groups long; see Figure 4 (left). Although it is clear that any single group can be removed without splitting the footprint, this can only be determined by traversing a path of length $4n - 1$ links.

For this reason, the implementation of the *retreat* operation in OOC is based on a stronger (sufficient but not necessary) property. More specifically, an uncovered base group can be removed if and only if it will not split the subset of the footprint contained in its Moore neighborhood into separate components. This stronger property can be enforced using only local rules.

Implementation of the *advance* operation presents a similar problem. To understand this, consider a roving pile with a square footprint like the one described above, but with a single group removed;

Figure 5: A covered base group at X with an empty *north* link can be replaced in the footprint by the group above it in the stack. Now unlinked, this *advance group* can be used to extend the footprint northward to N . This requires mapping the footprint in the neighborhood of N using search. Any base groups discovered at NW (left), NN (middle) and NE (right) become the advance group’s *west*, *north* and *east* links. The group that replaced it in the footprint at X becomes the advance group’s *south* link. Corresponding advance operations are performed in the other three cardinal directions. The four together depend only on the topology of the footprint inside a 5×5 neighborhood centered on X .

see Figure 4 (middle). In principle, an advance operation could fill the gap, completing the square. However, this would require a process able to determine whether or not base groups adjacent to the advance site are part of the same pile as itself. Again, this can only be done by traversing a path of length $4n - 1$ links.

The solution is to perform an exhaustive enumeration within the neighborhood surrounding the advance site; see Figure 5. This is done to avoid (as much as possible using local rules only), the situation where spatially adjacent regions of the footprint are not connected.

Observations of a working implementation show that roving piles remain flat (low average stack height) and connected. Smaller piles (those containing less than fifty actors) constantly evolve in shape while rapidly moving around the lattice on random walks. Holes created by expelling actors in uncovered base groups are quickly filled. Larger piles extend and retract pseudopod-like extensions but remain largely immobile in aggregate.

6.6 Pile Import Interface

Synthesis consumes primitives. The pipeline incorporates them into methods and zippers wherever local configurations permit method execution. Without replenishment, synthesis would exhaust the pile’s supply of primitives and halt.

The `request` combinator is the pile’s import interface. It introduces a third kind of event into the priority queue, distinct from diffusion and method execution. Each request event is associated with a specific primitive type. When a request is enqueued, an empty “proxy” group is placed inside the pile as a placeholder. When the request event reaches the front of the priority queue and is serviced, a primitive of the specified type is placed into the proxy group, replenishing the pile’s supply.

This mechanism has a notable consequence. Because each request specifies the type of the

primitive it imports, and because requests are generated by synthesis steps that consume specific types, the replenishment process automatically preserves the initial type histogram of the cytoplasm. Type composition is maintained not by explicit regulatory machinery but as a structural invariant of the request mechanism itself.

The time required to service a request is constant and independent of type. This corresponds to the well-stirred reactor assumption standard in artificial chemistry research Dittrich et al. [2001]: the cell resides in an infinite, well-mixed bath with a uniform primitive type histogram, so supply is inexhaustible and unbiased and the cost of replenishment does not depend on what is being replenished.

6.7 Genuine Parallelism under a Single Event Chronology

Any claim that synthesis or export is parallel would be suspect if pile-mediated transport were uncharged—if actors could be relocated without temporal cost, or if computation and transport inhabited separate temporal regimes. Neither is the case. The model admits a single event chronology: all state changes, whether diffusion of a group to an adjacent site or execution of a method, occur at times dictated by a single priority queue and paid for at the same rate. There is no secondary clock and no free background transport layer.

This has a direct consequence for how replication time should be understood. Because transport and computation are interleaved in the same stochastic history rather than composed additively, asking what fraction of replication time is consumed by transport is neither possible nor meaningful. The relevant question is whether transport extends the critical path through the global event chronology—and because all events are scheduled and priced by the same priority queue, transport can do so only by delaying a method execution that would otherwise have proceeded. That cost is already reflected in the replication times reported in Section 10.

The same principle applies to synthesis and export without distinction. A synthesis step requires the participating actors to be brought together by pile-mediated diffusion before the method can fire; a completed program-description pair reaches the daughter through the same globally ordered dynamics, not by fiat. The pile is therefore not a source of free parallelism. It is a spatially extended substrate whose transport capacity is realized by local diffusion events priced within the same chronology as method execution, and it is this shared chronology that makes the parallelism of the cell genuine rather than notional.

6.8 Summary

The roving pile device provides compartments without membrane physics. Isolation of cellular components, concentration of reactants, and transport of both reactants and products are all achieved by a single mechanism. Unlike a membrane, the roving pile requires no joint control of surface area and enclosed volume. The compartment boundary is defined combinatorially by the pile’s footprint, and its admissible moves are constrained by purely local tests. This locality permits implementation of roving piles on an ACA substrate, consistent with OCCC’s character as an abstract interface to indefinitely scalable distributed hardware.

The pile plays a deeper architectural role than compartmentalization alone. It is the spatially distributed substrate through which the cell’s concurrent processes communicate. Because communication is mediated by local pile dynamics rather than a centralized channel, concurrent processes can execute in parallel: the pile converts the concurrency of the method-based architecture into genuine

spatial parallelism. It isolates a cell’s components from those of other cells and the environment, preserves reactant concentrations so that synthesis pipelines can complete, and permits coordination of concurrent replication subproblems through local communication rather than centralized control.

The sections that follow extend roving piles to support multiple compartments separated by selectively permeable boundaries, and show how this capability is exploited to implement parallel export and fission.

7 Parallel Export and Organization

Until this point, we have treated self-replication largely as a problem of synthesizing component programs and their descriptions. However, as McMullin [2004] noted, an artificial cell must accomplish two tasks. First, it must reproduce its own components. Second, the components and their duplicates must be spatially organized into separate cells. If the organization process is symmetrical, then the separate cells are both *daughters*. However, if the organization process is asymmetrical (as in yeast which reproduce by budding), then the two cells are distinguishable and can be called *mother* and *daughter*.

7.1 Compartmentalization without Membrane Physics

Segregation of an organism’s component parts from those of other organisms can be accomplished in different ways. If organisms are defined solely as patterns of states inside compact, connected regions of a parallel substrate, then distance alone can serve this purpose. A daughter organism can be constructed at some offset relative to its mother using the device of a construction arm [von Neumann, 1966, Langton, 1984, Nehaniv, 2004]. Unfortunately, the use of this device eliminates the possibility of parallel speedup since it acts as a sequential bottleneck. Irrespective of the fact that it is spatially distributed and uses pipeline parallelism in its transmission of signals, the von Neumann automaton, considered as a whole, is sequential since the daughter automaton is constructed one site at a time at the tip of the moving construction arm.

Moveable organisms require a different solution. The most straightforward is to represent them as the connected components of a graph embedded in the substrate Hutton [2004]. In living cells, segregation is accomplished using membranes. Roving piles are a simpler alternative (Section 6), and in the present paper we extend them to support multiple compartments separated by selectively permeable boundaries. This permits export to be implemented as a spatially distributed process that resembles binary fission in living cells. The underlying mechanism is a topological complex that can be flattened, *i.e.* immersed in the plane, yielding a compartment footprint in the lattice. Figure 6 shows a simple two compartment model illustrating the mechanism in its most elementary form. Figures 7 and 8 show the more complex three compartment model used by the artificial cell described in this paper.

7.2 A Two-Compartment Pile: Cell and Vacuole

The simplest extension of a roving pile is to introduce a second compartment that functions as an isolated reservoir. Topologically, this can be obtained by identifying the inner boundary of an annulus with the boundary of a disc, yielding a footprint with two compartments called *cell* and *vacuole*; see Figure 6. The boundary between compartments is *selectively permeable*. Transport is mediated by a pair of combinators that act as a transport interface. These combinators modify

Figure 6: Topologically identifying the inner boundary of an *annulus* and the boundary of a *disc* creates the footprint of a roving pile with two compartments called *cell* and *vacuole*. The boundary between compartments is *selectively permeable*. Transport is mediated by a pair of combinators that act as a *transport interface* (right). These combinators modify *group state*. Groups in the *give* state can move (by diffusion) from cell to vacuole while groups in the *take* state can move in the opposite direction.

group state. Groups in the *give* state can move (by diffusion) from cell to vacuole while groups in the *take* state can move in the opposite direction.

The vacuole interface consists of three combinators. `seed` creates the vacuole compartment, establishing the inner disc whose boundary becomes the selectively permeable interface. `give` places the group containing an actor in the *give* state, permitting it to diffuse from cell to vacuole. `take` places the group containing an actor in the *take* state, permitting it to diffuse from vacuole to cell. As shown in Figure 6, the two-compartment device provides a clean model for controlled inter-compartment transport that generalizes naturally to the three-compartment fission device described next.

7.3 A Three-Compartment Pile: Mother, Daughter, and Septum

To model binary fission and to support parallel export, a stronger device is needed. Figure 7 shows a mother cell in the process of division. In three dimensions, a pair of circular apertures pierce the daughter cell membranes and the *septum* that divides the cell volume. The pair of apertures and the boundary of the septum are topologically identified along the course of the *contractile ring* (red). Adding a second circular aperture to each membrane at the end opposite the septum (blue and green) creates a topological complex that can be flattened.

The resulting planar immersion yields the footprint of a roving pile with three compartments called *mother*, *daughter* and *septum*. The boundary shared by the three compartments (red) is selectively permeable, mediated by four combinators. `open` places the group containing an actor in the *open* state, permitting it to diffuse from mother into the septum; `open'` implements the corresponding operation permitting diffusion from daughter into the septum. `close` places the group in the *close* state, permitting it to diffuse from septum back into mother; `close'` permits diffusion from septum into daughter. As Figure 7 shows, transfer from mother to daughter is accomplished by the composition `open >=> close'`, which routes a group through the septum; the convenience combinators `export` and `export'` name this composition in the two directions.

Figure 7: Exploded view in three dimensions of a cell in the process of binary fission showing a pair of circular apertures that pierce daughter cell membranes and the *septum* that divides the cell volume (left). The pair of apertures and the boundary of the septum are topologically identified along the course of the *contractile ring* (red). Adding a second circular aperture to each membrane at the end opposite the septum (blue and green) creates a *topological complex* that can be flattened, *i.e.*, *immersed* in the plane. This complex is the footprint of a roving pile with three compartments called *mother*, *daughter* and *septum*. The boundary shared by the three compartments (red) is selectively permeable. Export from mother to daughter is mediated by a set of combinators that act as an *export interface* (right). *Open* (or *close*) change group states to *open* (or *close*), conferring permission to diffuse from mother to septum (or *vice versa*). This causes the area of the septum to increase (or decrease), which increases (or decreases) the length of the shared boundary, controlling the rate of diffusion from mother to daughter of groups in export states.

7.4 Budding and Fission as $O(1)$ Local Compartment Surgery

A final device is needed to create a daughter compartment efficiently and to complete fission without employing non-local operations. Figure 8 shows an exploded view of mother cell with *bud* and the planar immersion of the corresponding complex (left). The septum's footprint is a square of size 1×1 , while the mother and daughter cell's footprints are annuli with square inner boundaries of size 1×1 (red). The outer boundary of the daughter cell's footprint is a square of size 3×3 (blue). Significantly, the footprints of the daughter and septum can be created using $O(1)$ operations in a single Moore neighborhood of the mother's footprint.

Figure 8 (right) shows the exploded view immediately prior to fission and the planar immersion of the complex. The group comprising the septum's footprint can be expelled and the resulting holes in mother and daughter filled using $O(1)$ operations in the septum's Moore neighborhood. This completes compartment fission without requiring a construction arm, global addressing, or any non-local boundary operation.

Five combinators implement budding and fission. **solid** is a guard that succeeds only if the actor's group is an uncovered base group whose Moore neighborhood is wholly interior to the pile; it

Figure 8: Exploded view of mother cell with *bud* and planar immersion of complex (left). The septum's footprint is a square of size 1×1 , while the mother and daughter cell's footprints are annuli with square inner boundaries of size 1×1 (red). The outer boundary of the daughter cell's footprint is a square of size 3×3 (blue). Significantly, the footprints of the daughter and septum can be created using $O(1)$ operations in a single Moore neighborhood of the mother's footprint. Exploded view of mother and daughter cell immediately prior to fission and planar immersion of complex (right). The footprint of the septum is a square of size 1×1 , while the footprints of the mother and daughter are annuli with square inner boundaries of size 1×1 . The group comprising the septum's footprint can be expelled and the resulting holes in mother and daughter filled using $O(1)$ operations in the septum's Moore neighborhood.

serves as a precondition for *bud*. *bud* takes a group *g* satisfying *solid* and an optional list of groups *h*. It constructs a unit septum containing *g* together with eight empty groups that comprise the initial footprint of the daughter pile. *g* receives exactly four *split* links in the cardinal directions, paired with four *join* links from the mother pile and four from the daughter pile. Any groups in *h* are placed in the daughter as its initial content. *smash* decomposes a composite into its constituent primitives, releasing them as actors in singleton groups into the pile; its idiomatic use is to inflate the septum and daughter compartments either directly, after *bud* has constructed their structural scaffolding, or by smashing actors exported into them via *open* and/or *close*'. *done* is a guard that succeeds only when the actor's group occupies a unit septum — a base group with exactly four split links paired with four joins from the mother pile and four joins from the daughter pile; it serves as a precondition for *cut*. *cut* closes the unit septum, severing all split/join links and separating mother and daughter into two independent piles, completing division.

Taken together, these compartment mechanisms make it possible for a cell hosted in OOC to export products from mother to daughter without introducing a sequential bottleneck. In the sections that follow we show how this capability is exploited to implement a self-replicating artificial cell whose synthesis pipeline and export process are both spatially distributed and amenable to parallel speedup.

8 Artificial Cell: Concrete Realization of the Architecture

The preceding sections argue that an evolvable system architecture must support (i) accumulation of complexity by duplication and specialization of modules, (ii) concurrency to mitigate the cost of increases in complexity through robustness, and (iii) parallelism to mitigate the cost through decreased replication time. Section 3 gave an extended von Neumann-style case study showing how execution-order constraints determine which replication strategies admit parallel speedup, and Section 7 described how roving-pile compartments permit export and fission to be implemented without introducing a sequential bottleneck.

In this section we describe a concrete artificial cell in OOC that instantiates these architectural ideas. The cell reproduces its own components using a spatially distributed asynchronous parallel pipeline, while simultaneously organizing duplicated components into mother and daughter compartments so that replication completes by fission. The purpose of the construction is not to claim this particular architecture is unique, or optimal, or even close to minimal. Rather, it serves as an existence proof: artificial cells can replicate using spatially distributed asynchronous parallel processes, and increased complexity can pay for itself by reducing replication time.

The cell’s concrete realization has three layers of machinery. At its core is a six-stage synthesis pipeline, implemented by programs A – F , that reproduces program descriptions by distributed translation and copying. Within that pipeline, the stages B and E are the principal rate-limiting steps, so additional copies of those programs provide the main controllable source of parallel speedup. In addition to executing its core synthesis pipeline, the cell must initiate synthesis, export synthesis products, and implement binary fission. These functions are carried out by programs X , Y , and Z . Roving piles provide the compartment structure that makes these synthesis and organization processes local, asynchronous, and genuinely parallel.

8.1 Programs and Control Structure

An artificial cell must accomplish two tasks. First, it must reproduce its own components. Second, the components and their duplicates must be spatially organized into separate cells. We implemented an artificial cell that accomplishes the first of these tasks using a parallel pipeline consisting of six programs A – F that translate and copy program descriptions; see Figure 3. The second task is accomplished by programs X , Y , and Z , which manage the organization of components and duplicates into mother and daughter cells. The lengths of the nine programs comprising the artificial cell are given in Table 1.

The roles of X , Y , and Z are distinct and sequential. X acts first: it creates the septum, places $\phi(X)'$ in the daughter, and then smashes itself to form the daughter cytoplasm. The bulk of X is a dummy payload carrying all the combinator types needed for method and zipper synthesis at the correct frequencies; this accounts for its length relative to Y and Z in Table 1. Y acts second: it is deliberately short — just eight combinators — and its sole architectural purpose is to serve as a trigger. When the daughter’s inherited pipeline A' – F' successfully translates $\phi(Y)'$, producing Y'' , this demonstrates that the daughter possesses a functional synthesis pipeline together with the full complement of inherited programs and descriptions. Because Y is short, this demonstration occurs as early as possible in the daughter’s replication cycle. Z acts third, in response to the trigger: having been produced by the daughter pipeline, Z' migrates to the septum, where it returns the mother zippers $\phi(x)$ sequestered there by F back to the mother cytoplasm, restarting the mother’s replication cycle. The restart therefore overlaps in time with the daughter’s own replication process;

Figure 9: Schematic diagram of artificial cell. Mother (green) and daughter (blue) are depicted immediately prior to fission. X seeds the daughter cytoplasm; the daughter pipeline $A'-F'$ then translates $\phi(Y)'$, producing the witness Y'' . This triggers Z' , which migrates to the septum, returns the sequestered mother zippers $\phi(x)$ to the mother cytoplasm, and closes the septum, completing fission. Parallel speedup results from extra copies of B and E .

see Figure 9. When Z' is the last actor remaining in the septum, it closes the septum and expels itself from the pile, completing fission.

This sequential handoff — X seeds, Y witnesses, Z releases and closes — is the control logic that coordinates replication without a centralized sequential bottleneck. Each step is triggered by a local event rather than by a global scheduler. Each exported program-description pair carries a short initialization sequence that installs it in its operational state on first execution in the daughter; the details of this device, while non-trivial, are beyond the scope of the present paper. The argument for why this handoff suffices to guarantee export correctness is developed in Section 8.2.

8.2 Export without a Sequential Bottleneck

The final stage of the synthesis pipeline is implemented by F . Given a completed pair $(x', \phi(x)')$, F packages the two objects into a single group in the *export* state. At the same time, F restores the mother zipper $\phi(x)$ to the conformation required by A , the first stage of the synthesis pipeline.

However, F does not immediately return $\phi(x)$ to productive use. Instead, it changes the state of the group containing $\phi(x)$ to *open*, causing that group to migrate to the septum. Thus F prepares the mother zipper for reuse while simultaneously withholding it from reuse until replication has completed.

This sequestration has two consequences. First, it reduces contention with the synthesis pipeline operating in the mother cytoplasm. Second, it prevents the mother from synthesizing unnecessary additional copies of x' and $\phi(x)'$ before the daughter has been completed. The zipper is therefore not merely a passive catalyst of synthesis; its temporary removal from circulation is part of the control logic that coordinates replication.

Sequestration is released only after the daughter has demonstrated that its own synthesis pipeline is functional. This demonstration takes the form of a constructive witness: because programs and descriptions are exported in pairs, successful synthesis of Y'' from $\phi(Y)'$ proves that the daughter possesses not only the inherited programs A', \dots, F' but also the inherited descriptions $\phi(A)', \dots, \phi(F)'$ together with $\phi(Y)'$. Since X' creates the septum and places $\phi(X)'$ in the daughter before smashing itself to form the daughter cytoplasm, any daughter capable of carrying out the later stages of the construction must also possess $\phi(X)'$. Finally, Z' migrates to the septum only after the daughter has successfully synthesized Y'' , and fission is completed only when Z' closes the septum. Thus septum closure cannot occur unless the daughter already contains the programs and descriptions needed to support that successful synthesis and the later closure event, including $\phi(Y)'$ and $\phi(Z)'$.

Export correctness is therefore established without any sequentially updated global record. Completeness is not tracked explicitly but inferred from a distributed constructive witness: the daughter's ability to translate and copy $\phi(Y)'$. That witness both proves that the daughter has received the required complement of inherited components and triggers the release of the mother zippers needed to begin the next replication cycle.

This mechanism differs fundamentally from that of Williams [2019]. In the earlier cell, the E stage reversed but did not copy, so the completed program and its description were not produced as a single exportable unit. Correct export therefore required a centralized checklist, represented as a single group whose state recorded which programs and descriptions had already been delivered to the daughter. Because many export operations needed to update this same shared state, the export process necessarily contained a sequential bottleneck. In the present cell, by contrast, E copies rather than merely reverses, and the pipeline completes x' and $\phi(x)'$ together. Pairwise export removes the need for a centralized checklist and replaces globally serialized bookkeeping with a local constructive witness.

8.3 Genuine Parallelism

The export process of the present cell is genuinely parallel: daughter components are exported in parallel across an extended one-dimensional interface separating mother and daughter, thereby avoiding a sequential bottleneck in daughter construction. This contrasts with the classical von Neumann architecture, which is often perceived as parallel because it resembles a spatially distributed parallel circuit. But its mode of daughter construction is fundamentally sequential. The issue is not that the von Neumann replicator lacks spatially distributed or parallel activity. Much of its machinery is in fact spatially distributed, and many of its operations can proceed in parallel. But these parallel activities do not determine the overall replication rate, because daughter construction contains a sequential bottleneck. The daughter is written into place one site at a time by the

Table 1: Program lengths (combinators).

A	B	C	D	E	F	X	Y	Z
42	62	55	63	74	92	89	8	43

construction arm, and this rate-limiting step serializes the process as a whole.

The present cell avoids this limitation by abandoning site-by-site daughter assembly. Daughter components are synthesized in parallel in the mother and transported through the pile and across the boundary via the same distributed process that mediates all other transport. What genuinely parallelizes export is that transfer occurs across an extended mother-daughter boundary rather than through a single point of passage. Multiple export events can therefore occur at different locations along that boundary, and because transport is a temporally extended physical process, these events can overlap in time. That temporal overlap is essential: without it, the operations comprising export across an extended interface could in principle be performed sequentially according to a schedule of equal duration.

This distributed process is fully costed. As shown in Section 6.7, method execution and pile-mediated transport inhabit the same global Gillespie-algorithm event chronology. Transport of a program-description group through the pile is a temporally extended physical process, not an uncharged abstraction, and its cost is already reflected in the replication times reported in Section 10. The singleton character of X , Y , and Z poses no difficulty: these actors merely verify daughter maturity and reinitiate the cell cycle in both mother and daughter. Export itself is mediated by actors across an extended boundary within the same substrate and under the same event chronology as every other process in the cell.

In the next section we show experimentally that increasing complexity by adding redundant copies of the programs implementing the rate-limiting stages of the synthesis pipeline can decrease replication time despite the increased costs of control and export.

9 Comparison with Hutton’s 2D Artificial Cells

Hutton’s 2D artificial cells [Hutton, 2004] are the principal antecedent of the present work, and its most natural point of comparison. His work demonstrated that a spatially embedded artificial chemistry can support self-reproducing cells exhibiting genuine parallelism, and that a small amount of contingent encoded information can be selectively advantageous. In particular, he constructed an environment in which a short gene encoding an enzyme is essential for reliable reproduction, and showed that cells carrying that gene are selectively favored. He also explicitly identified the central limitation of his construction: although the cells could in principle direct their entire reproduction sequence through encoded enzymes, this was not realized in practice, and the causal organization of reproduction remained almost entirely in the fixed chemistry.

This point is decisive for the present comparison. Under the definition adopted here, complexity is information subject to selection pressure. On this criterion, Hutton’s system contains only a trivial amount of contingent complexity relative to the total organization of the cell. Apart from the information contained in its short gene, Hutton’s entire cell is non-contingent structure replicated by its environment. The encoded gene does not specify the mechanisms underlying replication; those mechanisms are built into the fixed chemistry and are therefore non-contingent.

At the same time, Hutton’s cells exhibit genuine spatial parallelism: replication proceeds

concurrently at multiple locations in the substrate, and completion is achieved when mother and daughter elements are no longer connected. In this respect there is no export bottleneck. The difference between our cells and Hutton’s is not in the presence or absence of parallelism, but in its significance and its sources. In Hutton’s cells, the relevant parallelism is supplied by the chemistry and is therefore non-contingent. In our cells, the substrate likewise provides parallel material transfer by diffusion. This non-contingent source of parallelism is, however, of secondary importance. As shown by the analysis in Section 10.2, which neglects substrate-level parallelism entirely, the observed speedup arises from contingent duplication of functional modules and their descriptions, thereby increasing the copy numbers of the limiting stages of replication.

The two systems also employ closely related mechanisms of segregation. Although Hutton describes his cells as having membranes, they are really just 1D connected graphs embedded in a 2D substrate: there is no inside and outside in the stronger topological sense. The loop is the cell. The roving pile used here is likewise not a membrane in the sense of acting as a boundary between disjoint regions of space but is instead a 2D connected graph immersed in a 2D substrate. The more important distinction is that Hutton’s cells achieve segregation by means of a passive 1D data structure whereas the roving pile is an active 2D data structure equipped with multiple compartments and a combinator interface that the hosted computation uses for import, export, sequestration and fission.

These differences explain both the strength and the limitation of Hutton’s result. He showed that contingent encoded information can be adaptive in a spatially embedded chemical system. The present work addresses the problem he explicitly identified but did not solve: how to realize self-reproduction in an artificial cell possessing a non-trivial degree of semantic closure, a cell whose complexity resides primarily in its genome and is therefore subject to selection pressure, rather than in its environment. The claim is not that open-ended evolution has been demonstrated, but that an architecture has been constructed in which substantial increases in contingent complexity can, in principle, be supported by surplus capacity arising from parallel speedup.

10 Results and Discussion

The artificial cell described in Section 8 was designed so that replication time is dominated by the stages of the synthesis pipeline that require time proportional to genome length. In particular, stages *B* and *E* traverse zipper representations of program descriptions $\phi(x)$ and therefore require time proportional to $|\phi(x)|$, while all other stages require constant time. Replication time is measured as the simulated time elapsed from the initiation of a replication cycle to its completion; as established in Section 6.7, this time is computed under a single Gillespie-algorithm event chronology that accounts for the true costs of both method execution and pile-mediated transport. The purpose of this section is not to argue that the particular artificial cell described is the right architecture for artificial life, or that its mechanisms are optimal. The point is that it exists. It instantiates, in a single concrete system, the architectural thesis developed in Section 2 and operationalized by the execution-order analysis of Section 3: in sufficiently parallel systems, increased complexity can become selectable because parallelism can more than offset the additional replication cost that it would otherwise impose.

Figure 10: Artificial cell replication time in 10^4 operations (left scale) and mass in combinatorial units (right scale) as functions of number of copies of B and E . Error bars show $\pm\sigma$.

10.1 Replication Time Versus n

The artificial cell’s replication time as a function of the number of copies n of the B and E programs and descriptions was measured experimentally. A significant decrease in replication time relative to $n = 1$ was observed for $1 < n < 7$, consistent with parallel speedup. This speedup occurred despite the increased size of the artificial cells; see Figure 10. Replication time continued to decrease with increasing n before reaching a minimum value at $n = 5$ followed by a slight increase at $n = 6$. The $n = 1$ cell is substantially smaller (734 combinatorial units) than the cells with $n > 1$ (> 1872 combinatorial units at $n = 5$); see Table 1. Nevertheless, its replication time (405×10^4 operations) exceeds that of every cell with $n > 1$.

The pattern exhibited in Figure 10 is structurally identical to that observed in *E. coli*; compare Figure 1. In both cases, replication time and mass are plotted as functions of the copy number of the machinery implementing the rate-limiting step of synthesis — ribosomes in *E. coli*, and copies of B and E in the artificial cell. In both cases, replication time decreases as copy number increases despite increasing mass, and the speedup achieved is of the same order of magnitude: approximately $3\times$ in *E. coli* over the range shown, and approximately $2\times$ in the artificial cell.

10.2 A Simple Scheduling Model of Parallel Speedup

Section 3 showed, in the abstract setting of the von Neumann replicator, that parallel speedup depends on the structure of execution-order constraints imposed by shared resources and data dependencies, and that redundancy of the rate-limiting stages can divide the fixed cost of processing non-redundant descriptions among multiple pipeline instances. The experiments in Section 10 instantiate this analysis concretely. Figure 10 exhibits a speedup regime in which replication time is lower for larger cells than for smaller ones: replication time decreases as n increases, replication time reaches a minimum at $n \approx 5$, and then increases. A simple scheduling model explains why this speedup regime exists and why its extent is controlled by the number of non-redundant subproblems in the system.

There are $2n$ zippers representing $n_B = n_E = n$ copies each of methods B and E , together with the 7 single-instance zippers representing methods A, C, D, F, X, Y , and Z , for a total of $2n + 7$ zippers to be translated and copied. The makespan has three dominant contributions. First, the single-instance methods A, C, D, F must process all $2n + 7$ zippers sequentially, contributing

$$(N_A + N_C + N_D + N_F)(2n + 7).$$

This term grows linearly with n and acts as a penalty for increasing redundancy. Second, the $2n$ over-expressed zippers are processed by n pipeline instances in parallel, contributing the constant

$$2(N_B + N_E)^2.$$

Third, the single-instance zippers must also be traversed by methods B and E . Since method Y is negligible ($N_Y = 8$), this contributes

$$\frac{(N_B + N_E)(N_A + N_C + N_D + N_F + N_X + N_Z)}{\min(n, 6)}.$$

Combining all three contributions:

$$T(n) \approx (N_A + N_C + N_D + N_F)(2n + 7) + 2(N_B + N_E)^2 + \frac{(N_B + N_E)(N_A + N_C + N_D + N_F + N_X + N_Z)}{\min(n, 6)}.$$

Substituting the method lengths from Table 1 (with N_Y omitted) in the above equation yields

$$T(n) = 504n + 38756 + \frac{52224}{\min(n, 6)}.$$

The behavior of $T(n)$ is governed by the competition between the first and third terms. The third term decreases as additional pipeline instances divide the translation and copying work on the single-instance zippers, while the first term increases linearly because the single-instance methods must process an increasing total number of zippers. This decrease saturates at $n = 6$ because there are exactly six single-instance zippers of non-negligible length whose translation and copying can be distributed among pipeline instances; beyond this point, no further division of that work is possible, and the linear penalty dominates.

The model therefore predicts a minimum near $n = 6$, and a maximum speedup of $T(1)/T(6) \approx 1.8\times$, both in qualitative agreement with the experimentally observed optimum at $n \approx 5$ and speedup of approximately $2\times$ shown in Figure 10. The remaining discrepancy reflects the model's

idealizations: perfect load-balancing (i.e., no contention), the omission of transport latencies, and the representation of method execution time by combinator count alone, which undercounts the true cost of non-deterministic evaluation.

The model also yields a prediction about a counterfactual: what would happen if all six pipeline methods A – F were replicated n times rather than only methods B and E ? In that case, the $(2n + 7)$ factor in the first term of $T(n)$ would become $(2n + 7n)$ and would then also be divided by n , yielding $9(N_A + N_C + N_D + N_F)$ for large n . The linear penalty would therefore disappear. The third term would change as well. In the present architecture its denominator saturates at $\min(n, 6)$ because only six non-negligible single-instance zippers contribute to that part of the schedule. If methods A , C , D , and F were also over-expressed, that bottleneck would be removed. The third term would then split into two parts:

$$(N_B + N_E)(N_A + N_C + N_D + N_F) + \frac{(N_B + N_E)(N_X + N_Z)}{\min(n, 2)}.$$

The first is independent of n , and the second saturates once the two remaining opportunities for parallelism have been exploited. The model would then predict replication time decreasing monotonically toward a constant asymptote, with no upturn.

10.3 Surplus Capacity and the Replication of Arbitrary Payload

The cells with $2 \leq n \leq 5$ do not merely replicate faster than the $n = 1$ cell; they replicate faster while being substantially more massive. The difference in replication time between the $n = 5$ cell and the $n = 1$ cell is therefore surplus capacity: replication-time that is recovered by parallelism and not consumed by the additional pipeline machinery.

This surplus has a direct interpretation in von Neumann’s terms. A self-replicating system consists not only of the machinery required for replication — the translator A , copier B , and controller C — but also of a payload D . Surplus capacity could be used to offset the replication costs of payload whose organization is shaped by selection for tasks beyond replication itself. Within the experimentally observed surplus, such payload could be replicated without exceeding the replication-time budget of the $n = 1$ cell.

The scheduling model extends this observation to a theoretical limit. In the counterfactual case where all pipeline methods A – F are overexpressed n times rather than only B and E , the linear penalty term disappears and replication time decreases monotonically toward a constant asymptote. In this limit, the fixed cost of any payload that does not itself scale with n is divided among n pipeline instances and asymptotically vanishes from the replication time. The mechanism therefore has the capacity, in principle, to pay for arbitrarily large increases in contingent complexity, provided those increases do not themselves scale with n . The experiments instantiate this result in a specific and bounded case; the model establishes the corresponding asymptotic principle.

10.4 Why Execution-Order Constraints Matter

The discussion in Section 3 is not merely a didactic framing. It identifies a structural reason why parallel self-replication has been rare in artificial life systems. Parallel speedup is not obtained simply by running a sequential process on a parallel substrate. It requires a replication process whose subproblems are both (i) decoupled by modularization, and (ii) sufficiently unconstrained by execution-order dependencies. In the von Neumann decomposition, the tension is explicit: shared

resources (programs and their descriptions) introduce constraints of the form fx/fy and fx/gx . These constraints determine the space of legal schedules. They determine which kinds of redundancy yield speedup, and which do not. Without this analysis, it is easy to confuse a merely concurrent self-replicating system with one that can actually achieve increased fitness through parallelism.

The artificial cell in this paper works because its architecture deliberately attacks these constraints. The genome is modularized into separate zipper descriptions. The synthesis pipeline is explicitly designed so that the dominant work occurs in stages (B and E) that are parallelizable by over-expression. And, critically, export is engineered so that it does not introduce a sequential bottleneck.

The general point is that execution-order constraints are not an implementation detail. They are the ultimate determinants of whether or not an organism’s system architecture is capable of paying for increases in contingent complexity via surplus capacity.

10.5 Roving Piles as a General Compartment Device

The roving pile data structure (Section 6) is a separate contribution. It provides a method for compartmentalization, reactant concentration, and communication without requiring a membrane physics. It supports growth and motion by local operations, and it supports compartment interfaces (selective permeability) using purely computational mechanisms.

In the present paper, roving piles are used to implement mother/daughter organization, a septum, and fission in $O(1)$ local surgery steps. However, the device is not specific to this cell or to OOC. It is a general-purpose spatial data structure for representing compact embedded sets and is therefore a reusable building block for future organisms developed in OOC or other artificial chemistries. In particular, it supplies the compartmental isolation that prevents autocatalytic sets from degenerating into globally mixed reaction soups and that, as noted in Section 5, is the missing ingredient that converts an autocatalytic set into a *bona fide* artificial organism.

10.6 What Stronger Evidence Would Look Like

The present work establishes an existence proof, exhibits a clear speedup regime, and demonstrates surplus replication-time capacity that could in principle be occupied by arbitrary payload. There are at least three natural ways in which these results could be extended and tested more strongly.

First, the surplus-capacity argument of Section 10.3 can be tested by introducing explicit parasitic payload, namely additional combinators that contribute mass but not pipeline function, and showing that the speedup persists and that this payload is replicated within the $n = 1$ replication-time budget. The scheduling model makes a specific prediction about how the speedup regime shifts as payload mass increases, providing a quantitative test of the mechanism.

Second, one can test whether copy numbers can be optimized by evolution rather than set by the experimenter. Unlike Nakamura [2010], the parallel computation described in this paper is subject to race conditions that can affect its result. The export of *redundant* genes from mother to daughter is not completely reliable: because extra copies of B and E are unnecessary for synthesis of Y'' , unfinished copies are occasionally still in the mother when the septum closes. Since X is significantly longer than both B and E this happens only rarely, but when it does, the copy number in the current daughter decreases by one while the copy number in its younger sister increases by one. In a sufficiently large population this implies heritable variation in n_B and n_E and, in principle, in copy numbers n_j associated with other pipeline components as well. Given competition for scarce resources, natural selection should drive the distribution of these copy numbers toward

values that maximize fitness under the tradeoff between increased size, organizational cost, and increased parallelism. This would test whether the architecture supports adaptive movement through copy-number space toward locally optimal replication strategies.

Third, a stronger test would place the same architecture in a richer selective context. The claim of the present paper is not that open-ended growth of complexity has been demonstrated, but that the architectural conditions for such growth have been identified and instantiated. In the restricted environment studied here, the current cell may already be close to locally optimal for the task it performs. Additional organizational complexity would be expected to become advantageous only in settings where there is competition for finite resources, or in ecologies complex enough to support symbiosis, predator-prey dynamics, and host-parasite interactions [Bedau et al., 2000]. Those are the contexts in which one could ask whether duplication and specialization lead not merely to increased redundancy, but to the stable emergence of genuinely new functional modules.

The larger point is that these proposed tests are not afterthoughts. They follow from the structural commitments of the architecture itself: modularity, concurrency, and spatial parallelism. The execution-order framework developed in this paper makes those implications explicit, and the artificial cell provides a working platform in which they can be tested.

11 Conclusion

Reproduction by spatially distributed asynchronous parallel processes is essential for open-ended evolution of artificial organisms of increasing complexity. Despite this fact and the extensive literature on self-replicating systems, there has been little research on systems that replicate using parallel processes. This paper demonstrated that this omission is not inconsequential. Parallelism is not merely an optional convenience; it is an architectural principle that determines whether increased complexity is selected for or selected against.

More complex organisms are expensive: increased complexity entails increased mass, and increased mass entails increased work during replication. Absent parallelism, this creates a basic obstacle to the sustained accumulation of complexity under natural selection, because replication time is among the strongest determinants of fitness. In the natural world, living cells overcome this obstacle by massive redundancy of the limiting steps of replication, most notably by the over-expression of ribosomes. This is an instance of a more general mechanism: parallelism can allow complexity to pay for itself by reducing replication time despite increased size.

The central contribution of this paper is to make that mechanism explicit and operational. Section 2 developed the conceptual thesis that an evolvable system architecture must support modularity, concurrency, and parallelism. Section 3 showed, by an extended von Neumann-style case study, that the possibility of parallel speedup depends on execution-order constraints imposed by shared resources and data dependencies, and that architectural modifications, namely modularization of descriptions, redundancy of limiting processes, and pipelining, systematically enlarge the space of schedules supporting speedup.

We then described a concrete artificial cell defined in a combinator-based artificial chemistry that replicates using a spatially distributed asynchronous parallel pipeline, while organizing duplicated components into mother and daughter compartments by means of roving piles and completing replication by fission. Roving piles provide component isolation, reactant and product transport, and interprocess communication without requiring membrane physics. They are a computational analog of the compartmentalization that is a prerequisite for life, while remaining compatible with

purely local operations on an asynchronous cellular automaton substrate. Experimental results demonstrated significant replication-time speedup as redundant copies of the limiting pipeline stages were added and, more importantly, demonstrated a speedup regime in which larger cells reproduced in less time than smaller ones.

The main result is the identification and realization of a mechanism by which greater organizational complexity can repay its cost through reduced replication time via spatial parallelism. This is the architectural precondition for open-ended evolution of complexity. Alas, although we believe this precondition is strictly necessary, it is, by itself, insufficient. Several well-defined problems for future work follow immediately from the present results, as discussed in the preceding subsection.

The broader point is simple: for artificial life to demonstrate open-ended evolution of organisms of increasing complexity, it must acknowledge that biological life is a massively *parallel* computation.

Appendix: Spock Source for the Six-Stage Synthesis Pipeline

The following listings give the complete Spock source code for methods implementing stages A through F of the synthesis pipeline used by the artificial cell in the experiments. Each method executes repeatedly until its preconditions are no longer satisfied by actors in its pile neighborhood; together they implement the forward traversal (A–C), reverse traversal (D–F), and output production described in Section 5. Data flows right-to-left within a line; `=<<` is Kleisli composition applied right-to-left, so `f =<< g =<< h m` means: apply `h` to `m`, then `g`, then `f`.

Stage A: initiation of forward traversal

`lokA` recognizes the starting conformation of $\phi(x)$: a composite back `c` with a primitive focus at its hand bond, a single-primitive mother front at its prev bond, and *no* daughter front (the `none =<< prevs c` guard on line 3). It recruits a free primitive `n` whose type matches the first element of the back (the `similar` guard on line 5) and establishes it as the first element of the daughter front via `makePrev`. After `lokA` executes, the zipper carries paired fronts of length one and is in the mid-traversal conformation recognised by `lokB`.

Listing 1: Stage A.

```
lokA = spock [r|
  c <- amb =<< composite =<< ready =<< neighbors =<< quit =<< amb =<< ready m;
  some =<< primitive =<< hands c;
  none =<< prevs c;
  n <- amb =<< primitive =<< unbonded =<< ungrouped =<< ready =<< neighbors m;
  some =<< similar n =<< primitive =<< nexts c;
  makePrev c =<< join c =<< request n
|]
```

Note: `ready` ensures that a group is not in a transient state such as *open* or *close*?

Stage B: forward traversal step

`lokB` recognizes the mid-traversal conformation: a composite back `c` with a primitive focus `h` at the hand bond, a mother front `x` at the prev bond, and a daughter front `y` at the next bond. The guard on line 2 (`none =<< method =<< others c`) ensures that no other pipeline method is already handling this zipper, preventing concurrent interference. `lokB` extends both fronts by one combinator: the

mother front x receives a freshly recruited primitive n matching the focus (`compose x =<< request n`), while the daughter front y receives the focus itself after it is released (`compose y =<< drop h`). The zipper is then advanced: `decompose c` splits the back composite and `grab c` installs the recovered primitive as the new focus. `lokB` executes $|\phi(x)| - 2$ times, once for each interior element of the back; it is a rate-limiting stage and a primary target for parallelization.

Listing 2: Stage B.

```
lokB = spock [r|
  c <- amb =<< composite =<< neighbors =<< quit =<< amb =<< ready m;
  none =<< method =<< others c;
  h <- amb =<< primitive =<< hands c;
  x <- amb =<< prevs c;
  y <- amb =<< nexts c;
  n <- amb =<< primitive =<< unbonded =<< ungrouped =<< ready =<< neighbors m;
  some =<< similar h n;
  join c m;
  compose x =<< request n;
  compose y =<< drop h;
  grab c =<< join c =<< decompose c
|]
```

Stage C: terminal step of forward traversal

`lokC` recognizes the penultimate conformation: the back p is now a *primitive* (not a composite), meaning only one element of the back remains. The guard on line 3 requires that both fronts x and y are already composites, confirming this is the terminal rather than the starting conformation. `lokC` adds the final element to both fronts (`compose x =<< request n` and `compose y =<< drop h`) without advancing the zipper, leaving it focusless with both fronts holding the complete reversed description $\tilde{\phi}(x)$.

Listing 3: Stage C.

```
lokC = spock [r|
  p <- amb =<< primitive =<< neighbors =<< quit =<< amb =<< ready m;
  none =<< method =<< others p;
  h <- amb =<< primitive =<< hands p;
  x <- amb =<< composite =<< prevs p;
  y <- amb =<< composite =<< nexts p;
  n <- amb =<< primitive =<< unbonded =<< ungrouped =<< ready =<< neighbors m;
  some =<< similar h n;
  compose x =<< request n;
  compose y =<< drop h
|]
```

Stage D: initiation of reverse traversal

`lucD` recognizes the focusless conformation produced by `lokC`: a *handless* primitive back p with composite prev (x) and next (y) bonds, confirming both complete fronts are present. The guard `none =<< similar p =<< unbonded =<< others p` ensures that no matching free primitive is already grouped with p , preventing `lucD` from executing twice on the same zipper. `lucD` recruits a primitive

`n` matching the back's type and adds it to `p`'s group via `joinRequest`, forming a pair of backs. The zipper is now ready for the reverse pass by `lucE`.

Listing 4: Stage D.

```
lucD = spock [r|
  p <- amb =<< primitive =<< handleless =<< neighbors =<< quit =<< ready m;
  x <- amb =<< composite =<< prevs p;
  y <- amb =<< composite =<< nexts p;
  none =<< similar p =<< unbonded =<< others p;
  n <- amb =<< primitive =<< unbonded =<< ungrouped =<< ready =<< neighbors m;
  some =<< similar p n;
  joinRequest n =<< join p =<< request n
|]
```

Note: `joinRequest` is a convenience combinator that imports a primitive with similar type from outside the pile and adds it to an existing group rather than creating a new group like `request`.

Stage E: reverse traversal step

`lucE` recognizes the mid-reverse-traversal conformation: a `handleless` actor `p` with composite prev front `x` and composite next front `y`, and exactly two similar group members `q` and `r` forming the pair of backs. The `peek` combinator on line 8 finds a free primitive `z` whose type matches the leading element of the mother front `x` — the next primitive to be recovered — without consuming it. `lucE` then simultaneously advances both traversals: `compose p =<< decompose x` recovers the leading element from the mother front and pushes it onto the mother back `p`; `compose q =<< decompose y` does the same for the daughter front and back `q`; `compose r =<< request z` recruits and composes `z` onto the second daughter back `r`. `lucE` executes $|\phi(x)| - 1$ times; like `lokB`, it is a rate-limiting stage and a target for parallelization.

Listing 5: Stage E.

```
lucE = spock [r|
  p <- amb =<< handleless =<< neighbors =<< quit =<< amb =<< ready m;
  none =<< method =<< members p;
  x <- amb =<< composite =<< prevs p;
  y <- amb =<< composite =<< nexts p;
  s <- similar p =<< others p;
  q <- amb s;
  r <- amb =<< different q s;
  z <- amb =<< peek x =<< primitive =<< unbonded =<< ungrouped =<< ready =<< neighbors m;
  join p m;
  compose p =<< decompose x;
  compose q =<< decompose y;
  compose r =<< request z
|]
```

Stage F: completion

Stage F is the most complex stage. It recognizes the terminal conformation of the reverse traversal: a composite back `p` with a primitive prev `x` (the last element to be restored), no focus at the

hand, no other method in its group, and two similar group members `q` and `r` forming the daughter backs. The guard `none ==<< same x ==<< amb ==<< primitive ==<< nexts p` distinguishes this terminal conformation from the mid-traversal conformation handled by `lucE`.

`lucF` produces three outputs in a single committed action sequence. First, the mother zipper is reconstructed: `grab p ==<< join p ==<< decompose ==<< deletePrev p` removes the terminal prev bond, decomposes the final back element, and installs the recovered primitive as the new focus, restoring $\phi(x)$ to its starting conformation. Second, the daughter enzyme is produced: `quit ==<< compose q ==<< quit x` separates `x` from the mother, composes it onto the daughter back `q`, and ejects it; `join q r` merges the two daughter backs into a single composite ready for unquoting. Third, the daughter zipper is constructed: `makeNext r ==<< join r ==<< request z` recruits a matching primitive `z` and establishes it as the daughter front; `grab r ==<< join r ==<< decompose r` splits `r` and installs the recovered primitive as the daughter focus, placing $\phi(x)'$ in the starting conformation. Finally, `open p` marks the mother zipper for export to the septum; `unquote q` promotes the daughter composite to an executable method; and `grip m` marks the `lucF` method with a self-hand bond, preventing it from being applied again until the daughter has been confirmed viable.

Listing 6: Stage F.

```
lucF = spock [r|
  p <- amb ==<< composite ==<< neighbors ==<< quit ==<< amb ==<< ready m;
  x <- amb ==<< primitive ==<< prevs p;
  none ==<< method ==<< members p;
  none ==<< hands p;
  s <- similar p ==<< others p;
  q <- amb s;
  r <- amb ==<< different q s;
  none ==<< same x ==<< amb ==<< primitive ==<< nexts p;
  z <- amb ==<< similar x ==<< primitive ==<< unbonded ==<< ungrouped ==<< ready ==<< neighbors m;
  grab p ==<< join p ==<< decompose ==<< deletePrev p;
  quit ==<< compose q ==<< quit x;
  join q r;
  makeNext r ==<< join r ==<< request z;
  grab r ==<< join r ==<< decompose r;
  open p;
  export ==<< unquote q;
  grip m
]
```

Note: `different` returns elements of its first argument not found in its second argument.

References

- David H. Ackley. Bespoke physics for living technology. *Artificial Life*, 19(3–4):347–364, 2013.
- Chris Adami, C. Titus Brown, and W.K. Kellogg. Evolutionary learning in the 2D artificial life system “Avida”. In *Artificial Life IV*, pages 377–381. MIT Press, 1994.
- Chris Adami, Charles Ofria, and Travis C. Collier. Evolution of biological complexity. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 97(9):4463–4468, 2000. doi: 10.1073/pnas.97.9.4463.
- Mark A. Bedau et al. Open problems in artificial life. *Artificial Life*, 6(4):363–376, 2000.

- C. H. Bennett. Logical depth and physical complexity. In *A Half-century Survey on The Universal Turing Machine*, pages 227–257. Oxford University Press, 1988. ISBN 0-19-853741-7.
- Piotr Berman and Janos Simon. Investigations of fault-tolerant networks of computers. In *STOC*, pages 66–77, 1988.
- Ha Bremer and Patrick Dennis. Modulation of chemical composition and other parameters of the cell by growth rate. *E Coli Salmonella Cell Mol Biol*, 2, 01 1996.
- S. Carroll. Chance and necessity: the evolution of morphological complexity and diversity. *Nature*, 409:1102–1109, 2001.
- Stephen A. Cook and Robert A. Reckhow. Time-bounded random access machines. *Journal of Computer and System Sciences*, 7(4):354–375, 1973.
- David Deutsch. *The Fabric of Reality*. Penguin Press, 1997.
- Peter Dittrich, Johannes C Ziegler, and Wolfgang Banzhaf. Artificial chemistries: a review. *Artificial Life*, 7(3):225–275, 2001.
- Gerald M. Edelman and Joseph A. Gally. Degeneracy and complexity in biological systems. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 98(24):13763–13768, 2001.
- J. Doyne Farmer, Stuart A Kauffman, and Norman H Packard. Autocatalytic replication of polymers. *Physica D: Nonlinear Phenomena*, 22(1):50 – 67, 1986.
- Walter Fontana and Leo W Buss. *The barrier of objects: From dynamical systems to bounded organizations*. International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis, 1996.
- Allan Force, Michael Lynch, F. Bryan Pickett, Angel Amores, Yi-Lin Yan, and John Postlethwait. Preservation of duplicate genes by complementary, degenerative mutations. *Genetics*, 151(4): 1531–1545, 1999.
- Robert A Freitas and Ralph C Merkle. *Kinematic self-replicating machines*. Landes Bioscience, 2004.
- Murray Gell-Mann and Seth Lloyd. Effective complexity. Technical Report 03-12-068, Santa Fe Institute, 2003.
- Daniel T. Gillespie. Exact stochastic simulation of coupled chemical reactions. *The Journal of Physical Chemistry*, 81(25):2340–2361, 1977.
- Nicolas Glansdorff, Ying Xu, and Bernard Labedan. The last universal common ancestor: emergence, constitution and genetic legacy of an elusive forerunner. *Biology Direct*, 3(1):29, Jul 2008.
- Carl Hewitt, Peter Bishop, and Richard Steiger. A universal modular ACTOR formalism for artificial intelligence. In *Proceedings of the 3rd International Joint Conference on Artificial Intelligence (IJCAI)*, pages 235–245, 1973.
- Simon Hickinbotham, Edward Clark, Adam Nellis, Susan Stepney, Tim Clarke, and Peter Young. Maximizing the adjacent possible in automata chemistries. *Artificial Life*, 22(1):49–75, 2016.

- Gérard Huet. Functional pearl: The zipper. *Journal of Functional Programming*, 7(5):549–554, September 1997.
- Tim J. Hutton. A functional self-reproducing cell in a two-dimensional artificial chemistry. In *Proc. of the 9th Intl. Conf. on the Simulation and Synthesis of Living Systems (ALIFE)*, pages 444–449, 2004.
- A. N. Kolmogorov. Three approaches to the quantitative definition of information. *Problems of Information Transmission*, 1(1):1–7, 1965.
- Richard A. Laing. Automaton models of reproduction by self-inspection. *Journal of Theoretical Biology*, 66(1):437–456, 1977.
- Christopher G Langton. Self-reproduction in cellular automata. *Physica D: Nonlinear Phenomena*, 10(1):135–144, 1984.
- Julius Lukeš, John M. Archibald, Patrick J. Keeling, W. Ford Doolittle, and Michael W. Gray. How a neutral evolutionary ratchet can build cellular complexity. *IUBMB Life*, 63(7):528–537, 2011. ISSN 1521-6551.
- John Maynard Smith and Eörs Szathmáry. *The Major Transitions in Evolution*. Oxford University Press, Oxford, 1995.
- John McCarthy. A basis for a mathematical theory of computation. In P. Braffort and D. Hirschberg, editors, *Computer Programming and Formal Systems*, pages 33–70. North-Holland, Amsterdam, 1963.
- Barry McMullin. Thirty years of computational autopoiesis: A review. *Artificial life*, 10:277–95, 02 2004. doi: 10.1162/1064546041255548.
- Ron Milo and Rob Phillips. *Cell biology by the numbers*. CRC Press, 2015.
- Eugenio Moggi. Notions of computation and monads. *Information and Computation*, 93(1):55–92, 1991.
- K. Nakamura. Asynchronous cellular automata and their computational ability. *System Comput. Controls*, 15(5):56–66, 1974.
- Katsuhiko Nakamura. Asynchronous parallel self-replication based on logic molecular model. In *Proc. of the 12th Intl. Conf. on the Simulation and Synthesis of Living Systems (ALIFE)*, pages 403–410, 2010.
- Sasithorn Nakjang et al. Reduction and expansion in microsporidian genome evolution: New insights from comparative genomics. *Genome Biology and Evolution*, 5(12):2285–2303, 2013. doi: 10.1093/gbe/evt184.
- Chrystopher L. Nehaniv. Asynchronous automata networks can emulate any synchronous automata network. *IJAC*, 14(5-6):719–739, 2004.
- Allen P Nutman et al. Rapid emergence of life shown by discovery of 3,700-million-year-old microbial structures. *Nature*, 537:535–538, 2016.

- Howard H. Pattee. Evolving self-reference: Matter, symbols, and semantic closure. *Communications and Cognition*, 28(2–3):105–119, 1995.
- Jose B Pereira-Leal, Emmanuel D Levy, and Sarah A Teichmann. The origins and evolution of functional modules: lessons from protein complexes. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 361(1467):507–517, 2006. doi: 10.1098/rstb.2005.1807.
- Thomas S. Ray. An evolutionary approach to synthetic biology, Zen and the art of creating life. *Artificial Life*, 1:179–209, 1994.
- Matthew Scott and Terence Hwa. Bacterial growth laws and their applications. *Current Opinion in Biotechnology*, 22(4):559–565, 2011. doi: 10.1016/j.copbio.2011.04.014.
- Matthew Scott, Carl W. Gunderson, Eduard M. Mateescu, Zhongge Zhang, and Terence Hwa. Interdependence of cell growth and gene expression: Origins and consequences. *Science*, 330(6007):1099–1102, 2010. doi: 10.1126/science.1192588.
- Moshe Sipper. Fifty years of research on self-replication: An overview. *Artificial Life*, 4(3):237–257, 1998.
- Temple F. Smith and Michael S. Waterman. Identification of common molecular subsequences. *Journal of Molecular Biology*, 147(1):195–197, 1981.
- Ekaterina Sokolova et al. Enhanced transcription rates in membrane-free protocells formed by coacervation of cell lysate. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 110(29):11692–11697, 2013.
- Tim Taylor et al. Open-ended evolution: Perspectives from the OEE workshop in York. *Artificial Life*, 22(3):408–423, 2016.
- Kurt H. Thearling and Thomas S. Ray. Evolving parallel computation. *Complex Systems*, 10(3):229–237, 1996.
- John von Neumann. Theory of self-replicating automata. *Urbana: University of Illinois Press*, 1966.
- Philip Wadler. Comprehending monads. In *Proc. of the 1990 ACM Conf. on LISP and Functional Programming*, LFP '90, 1990.
- James D. Watson and Francis H. Crick. Molecular structure of nucleic acids. *Nature*, 171(4356):737–738, 1953.
- Lance R. Williams. Programs as polypeptides. *Artificial Life*, 22(4):451–482, 2016.
- Lance R. Williams. Towards complex artificial life. In *Conference on Artificial Life (ALIFE)*, pages 292–299, 2019.
- Brenda Youngren, Henrik Jörk Nielsen, Suckjoon Jun, and Stuart Austin. The multifork *Escherichia coli* chromosome is a self-duplicating and self-segregating thermodynamic ring polymer. *Genes and Development*, 28(1):71–84, 2014.